

Tennessee's Burden: How Students Apply for State Financial Aid Within One Southern State

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Abstract

Administrative burden, or the frictions individuals experience in accessing public programs, has implications for whether and which eligible individuals receive aid. While prior research documents barriers to accessing federal financial aid, less is known about the extent to which state aid programs impose administrative burden, how administrative burden varies across aid programs, or how administrative burden relates to target populations. This study examines administrative burden in 23 state aid programs in Tennessee. We find programs targeting less-advantaged students (technical and community college students) had lower burdens than programs where aid could be used in the four-year sector or across sectors. The state's only program explicitly targeting racially minoritized students had a significantly higher burden than other aid programs. Programs targeting more-advantaged students (merit-aid programs, students at four-year colleges and universities) had similar burdens relative to other programs. We discuss implications for designing more equitable and effective state aid programs.

Keywords: administrative burdens, higher education, state policy, financial aid, free college

State spending on financial aid totaled \$11.5 billion for students in public higher education in 2020 (Laderman & Heckert, 2021). These funds support various types of aid programs, often within a single state, including programs that target funds based on financial need, academic merit, enrollment in specific institution types, and other factors. States use aid programs to help achieve goals, such as improving college affordability, increasing educational attainment, meeting workforce needs, and reducing inequities in college enrollment and completion. While research indicates that financial aid can, under certain conditions, improve student outcomes and reduce economic and racial inequities in enrollment and completion (Monarrez et al., 2021; Nguyen et al., 2019), how state policymakers design and implement aid programs may impact whether particular programs are effective and equitable.

Administrative burdens, or the frictions individuals experience as they navigate the bureaucratic processes required to access public services and programs (Burden et al., 2012; Herd & Moynihan, 2018), are a known component of the financial aid application process (Moynihan et al., 2015; Rosinger et al., 2021). The extent to which federal and state governments impose administrative burdens affects who receives aid given that burdens disproportionately fall on low-income and racially minoritized individuals (Herd & Moynihan, 2018; Ray et al., 2022). As a result, more onerous programs with higher levels of administrative burden may be less effective in meeting state goals and addressing economic and racial inequities (Gándara et al., 2022).

While much is known about barriers to accessing federal aid, particularly the complexity associated with the Free Application for Federal Student Aid (FAFSA) (Bird & Castleman, 2016; Dynarski & Wiederspan, 2012; Kofoed, 2017), we know less about how students access state aid. Rosinger et al. (2021) examined state free college programs and found that the FAFSA was

just one of several requirements. States may also require program applications, documentation of grades, income, or volunteer activities, a certain high school and/or college GPA, and stringent enrollment requirements (e.g., enrollment immediately after high school or full-time and continuous enrollment). In addition, we know little about whether eligibility restrictions or application processes that contribute to administrative burden change over time.

Finally, states frequently operate several aid programs simultaneously with varying target populations, such as students with financial need, racially minoritized students, students meeting academic thresholds, and students at technical, community, and/or four-year colleges. Prior research indicates that aid programs in the state of Michigan impose different requirements on recipients (Steel et al., 2021), but we have little information regarding whether this is a single state phenomenon or if it happens in other states as well. In addition, we do not know whether and how the level of administrative burden relates to the aid program's target population.

The theory of the social construction of target populations can explain how policy design can be used to favor positively constructed and more politically powerful groups over less politically powerful groups (regardless of whether this latter group is positively or negatively constructed) (Ingram et al., 2019; Schneider & Ingram, 1993). As a result, policymakers may design aid programs that target more politically powerful and more-advantaged students and their families, such as students meeting some type of academic threshold or students at four-year colleges, to be less burdensome than those that target less-advantaged students and their families, such as low-income students, racially minoritized students, or students at technical or community colleges. Alternatively, institutions and industries may also wield a form of political power that can inform policy design, especially in the context of aid programs targeting technical and

community college students who attend institutions that provide workforce training and development.

Drawing on theories of administrative burden and the social construction of target populations, this study extends research on financial aid complexity by documenting and examining how the level of administrative burden varies across aid programs within a state, whether the level of administrative burden changes over time, and how the level of administrative burden relates to programs' target population. We focus on Tennessee because it is often seen as an innovator in state higher education policy. Tennessee was an early adopter of performance funding, broad-based merit aid (HOPE Scholarship), free college (Promise), and free college focused on helping adults complete a degree (Reconnect). Many of these state policies have served as a model for other states, and the state's efforts have been recognized nationally by the Obama administration and foundations, such as Gates and Lumina (Finney et al., 2017). In this study, we ask:

Research Question 1 (RQ1): To what extent do administrative burdens vary across state aid programs in Tennessee?

Research Question 2 (RQ2): To what extent do administrative burdens vary within state aid programs over time in Tennessee?

Research Question 3 (RQ3): How does administrative burden relate to whether the target population of a state aid program in Tennessee is relatively more or less advantaged?

To answer these questions, we reviewed state legislation and aid websites for 23 Tennessee aid programs from Fiscal Years 2011 to 2024. The resulting dataset documents the presence or absence of 27 program features, drawing on the typology created by Rosinger et al.

(2021) to identify features of state aid programs that are likely to contribute to administrative burden. We find that the only aid program explicitly focused on racially minoritized students also imposed one of the highest levels of administrative burden on intended recipients. In other cases, however, programs targeted toward less-advantaged students (technical and community college students) proved less onerous while programs targeted toward relatively more-advantaged students had similar levels of burden as other programs. This study expands our understanding of complexity in state aid and offers insight for state policymakers in designing aid programs that can more equitably and effectively meet state goals.

Conceptual Framework

We rely on a conceptual framework that pairs administrative burden (Herd & Moynihan, 2018) with the theory of the social construction of target populations (Ingram et al., 2019; Schneider & Ingram, 1993) in our study of state aid programs. Administrative burdens occur when an individual's experience navigating bureaucratic procedures exercising their rights or accessing public programs is onerous (Burden et al., 2012). In addition, administrative burdens occur across the public domain, from healthcare (Herd & Moynihan, 2020; Moynihan et al., 2016) and food programs (Hanratty, 2006), to immigration (Heinrich, 2018) and natural disasters (Connolly et al., 2021).

Administrative burdens that are embedded in public programs impose learning, compliance, and psychological costs on potential recipients (Moynihan et al., 2015). For instance, learning costs arise as potential financial aid recipients explore their aid options, assess their eligibility for aid, and learn how to apply for aid. Compliance costs arise as potential recipients seek to comply with application requirements and eligibility restrictions associated with aid programs. Finally, potential recipients may face psychological costs and/or stigma

associated with being deemed “low income,” having to repeatedly document their “low-income” status, or meet other stringent aid requirements (Moynihan et al., 2015; Rosinger et al., 2021).

The learning, compliance, and psychological costs that administrative burdens impose can prevent eligible individuals from receiving public benefits, and they fall disproportionately on racially minoritized and low-income individuals who often have less support navigating complex processes (Herd & Moynihan, 2018). Administrative burdens can contribute to structural racism in administrative practices by ensuring certain outcomes that reproduce racial inequities (Ray et al., 2022). As a result, although financial aid programs have the potential to increase college completion and fulfill workforce demands, administrative burdens may hinder students from applying for or maintaining aid, serving to reinforce inequities in college enrollment and completion. By contrast, reduction in the costs associated with program rules is related to higher take-up rates (Fox et al., 2022), which can lead to aid program designs that are more effective at reaching their target populations and that have greater potential to reduce inequities (Gándara et al., 2022; Rosinger et al., 2021).

Given the implications administrative burdens hold for the effectiveness and equity of state financial aid programs, our study aims to document and investigate the extent to which administrative burdens vary across aid programs in a single state (RQ1). Since administrative burdens are constructed by policymakers who design policies and street-level bureaucrats (SLBs), such as aid commissions and high school counselors, who implement policies (Herd & Moynihan, 2018), they may also change as the state’s political environment, demographics, and financial aid landscape changes. Therefore, we also investigate the extent to which burdens change over time within aid programs (RQ2).

Since aid programs within a single state are often targeted toward different populations, we couple the concept of administrative burden with the theory of the social construction of target populations to explore how the process of accessing aid varies depending on the targeted population (RQ3). The theory of social construction of target populations offers insight into how policies vary in their design depending on the social construction of targeted groups as deserving (or not) of aid and the amount of political power the target group wields. In particular, policymakers may ascribe different benefits and burdens on intended recipients depending on recipients' social construction and political power (Ingram et al., 2019; Schneider & Ingram, 1993).

Administrative burdens may be one part of this given that burdens are constructed by policymakers and can be used to allocate resources to individuals the public perceives as more deserving of aid (Herd & Moynihan, 2018). Following this logic, legislators may design aid programs with social constructions of target populations, and their political power, in mind and apply varying levels of administrative burden to each targeted population accordingly. Given that many state aid programs explicitly target low-income or other underserved populations, we must be wary of the ways in which habituated patterns of power and advantage are coded into the application process and reinforce inequities.

Schneider and Ingram (1993) identify four types of target populations with different social constructions (positive vs. negative) and political power (weak vs. strong): advantaged (positively constructed and politically strong), contenders (negatively constructed and politically strong), dependents (positively constructed and politically weak), and deviants (negatively constructed and politically weak). In this study, we focus primarily on two types of target populations: advantaged and dependents. Advantaged groups are positively constructed as

deserving of aid and wield substantial political power. Prior research has found that support for free college programs is stronger when the public perceives the target population as more deserving of aid, for instance, when students qualify based on high school GPA (Bell, 2020). Merit aid disproportionately benefits children from middle- and upper-income families (Heller & Marin, 2004), groups that also hold more political power (Leighley & Nagler, 2013). In fact, politicians trying to secure middle-class votes might privilege these voter's children in policy construction as a way to appeal to the median voter (see Holcombe (1989)). We anticipate that aid programs that are targeted toward more-advantaged students (and their families), who also tend to wield more political power (i.e., students meeting academic qualifications or aid targeted to students at four-year universities), will face lower levels of administrative burden.

In contrast, dependent groups have little political power even if they are positively constructed. Policies for dependent groups offer benefits but simultaneously tend to label or stigmatize recipients, require recipients to document their need, or prohibit and/or require certain actions of recipients (Ingram et al., 2019; Schneider & Ingram, 1993). It is difficult to determine how positively certain student groups are constructed in relation to student financial aid. Students from lower-income families or racially minoritized backgrounds may be positively constructed if a policy goal is to promote economic and racial equity. And yet, prior research indicates that the public views aid programs as less fair when a target population, such as lower-income students, wields less political power (Bell, 2020). As a result, programs that are targeted toward less politically powerful students, such as lower-income and racially minoritized students or students at technical and community colleges that disproportionately serve students from underserved backgrounds (Bailey et al., 2015), may be designed in ways that make aid more difficult to access by requiring eligibility documentation and restricting or requiring certain types of action.

We anticipate that programs that target less-advantaged and less politically powerful populations (i.e., lower-income, racially minoritized, technical or community college students) will have higher levels of administrative burdens relative to other programs. Alternatively, we could also envision a scenario in which the targeted populations of aid programs for technical and community college students are the institutions themselves and the industries that rely on the workforce training and development the institutions provide. In this case, the targeted population would be politically powerful, and policymakers seeking support from industry leaders may make financial aid targeted toward students at technical and community colleges easier to access to promote workforce development. We present these competing hypotheses for programs targeted toward students at technical and community colleges given the reality that this group could be positively or negatively constructed.

Literature Review

State spending on financial aid in many contexts is associated with increased enrollment and completion (Monarrez et al., 2021; Nguyen et al., 2019). Yet, despite increases in state spending on aid (Laderman & Kunkle, 2022), college enrollment and completion has not expanded at the same rate for low-income and racially minoritized students (Bailey & Dynarski, 2011; Baker et al., 2018). Prior research has considered various factors that contribute to economic and racial disparities in college enrollment and completion, including non-financial factors, such as how a complex college-going process contributes to inequitable outcomes (see Dynarski et al. (2022)).

Much of the work on complexity in the college-going process concentrates on applying for federal student aid (Dynarski & Wiederspan, 2012). The FAFSA, which is required for federal student aid, is a long and complex form (Dynarski & Scott-Clayton, 2006). Each year,

many potentially eligible students do not submit the FAFSA because they are not aware of federal aid or how to apply for it or report that the form is too complex (Rosinger & Ford, 2019). In addition, after enrolling in college, many students do not re-file the FAFSA, which is required to continue receiving federal aid (Bird & Castleman, 2016). State aid programs frequently require students to complete the FAFSA but often place additional eligibility restrictions and application requirements on potential recipients. State aid programs may require students to submit program applications (sometimes in addition to FAFSA), submit documentation to verify financial need, academic merit, or other criteria, meet deadlines to apply for aid, sign pledges or promissory notes, meet citizenship and residency requirements, perform volunteer service, and/or meet other program requirements or restrictions (Rosinger et al., 2021).

Complexity in federal and state financial aid program design has material consequences for students. Annually, eligible college students do not receive an estimated \$24 billion in grants and loans for which they are eligible (Kofoed, 2017). Even for students who previously received aid, many do not re-file the FAFSA and therefore do not receive federal aid (Bird & Castleman, 2016). Similar patterns emerge in state aid programs. For instance, the initial take-up rate for New York's free college program is estimated at 25 percent of potentially eligible students, and only around half of recipients maintained the scholarship in their second year (Scott-Clayton et al., 2022). Research has found that reducing barriers to FAFSA completion—such as providing assistance with the application and sending personalized reminders about FAFSA (Bettinger et al., 2012; Castleman & Page, 2015, 2016)—can improve college enrollment and completion.

Recent work has begun to investigate administrative burdens in state aid programs, often focusing on SLBs, such as high school counselors, who help implement state aid programs and can help to either mediate or exacerbate administrative burdens that students face (Lipsky, 1980).

Bell and colleagues (2020) surveyed SLBs who helped implement Oklahoma's Promise aid program and found that conservative SLBs were more supportive of administrative burden, often justifying burdens as a way to reduce fraud, prevent abuse, and demonstrate that students have earned or deserve aid. In contrast, liberal SLBs were less supportive of burdens and were more likely to view them as barriers that undermine social equity goals (Bell et al., 2020). The support and perceptions SLBs have for administrative burden are particularly important given subsequent research showing that high school counselors have discretionary power to either increase or decrease the burden students face in accessing the program (Bell & Smith, 2022). Billings and colleagues (2022) found that high school counselors themselves face administrative burdens in understanding the financial aid process and helping students apply and frequently turn to other counselors in their networks for assistance.

While prior literature offers insight into how SLBs experience, perceive, and help students navigate administrative burdens in state aid programs, we know relatively little about the student experience of applying for aid at the state level, particularly the extent to which students encounter administrative burden in accessing aid. A study by Rosinger and colleagues (2021) sought to quantify the level of administrative burden students face in accessing statewide free college programs by documenting the process of applying for and maintaining free college aid across states. They found that free college programs varied substantially across states in the administrative burden imposed on students.

The present study applies Rosinger et al.'s (2021) framework of measuring administrative burden on a broader set of state aid programs. Free college programs, the primary focus of literature on administrative burden in state aid (e.g., Bell et al., 2020; Bell & Smith, 2022; Rosinger et al., 2021), represent a growing but small amount of state funding for aid (Mishory &

Granville, 2019). States frequently operate multiple aid programs targeted toward different groups of students (National Association of State Student Grant and Aid Programs (NASSGAP), 2020), and these programs can impose different requirements for initial and continued receipt (Steel et al., 2021). However, we know relatively little about the administrative burden associated with applying for state aid, how it varies across aid programs within a state, and how the level of administrative burden relates to a program's targeted population, which this study examines using the state of Tennessee as a case site. In addition, the consideration of administrative burden in the design of aid programs may help explain the contexts in which aid can be more (or less) effective and equitable.

Data and Methods

State Selection and Context

As noted previously, we chose to focus on the state of Tennessee since it has served as a frequent model for other state aid programs, including broad-based merit aid and free college programs. In 2019-2020, Tennessee provided \$480 million in financial aid, the eighth-highest amount in the country (NASSGAP, 2020). Just under 60 percent of these funds were awarded through merit-based aid programs, around 20 percent through need-based aid programs, 5 percent through a combination of need- and merit-based programs, and the remainder through special purpose funds (such as a two teaching fellows programs, which include academic criteria) (authors' calculations from NASSGAP (2020)). The state funds 29 aid programs through general fund or lottery revenues (authors' review of state documents). This study focuses on 23 programs available to college students across the state. We excluded six aid programs that were either focused on current high school students or that offered tuition assistance as an employee benefit (rather than a free-standing financial aid program).¹ Thus, our study focuses on

the universe of grant aid programs directed to college students in the state. Table 1 includes information about each program and Appendix A offers detailed descriptions of each program and its requirements (Appendix B lists programs excluded from our study).

[Table 1 Here]

Tennessee’s funding of financial aid goes back nearly 50 years, with the introduction in 1976 of the Tennessee Student Assistance Award (TSAA) for students with financial need, which remains the state’s primary need-based aid program today. In the 2000s, the state expanded its aid programs, particularly with the introduction of the Tennessee Education Lottery Scholarship (TELS) program in 2004. TELS-funded programs are intended to improve high school academic achievement, promote college access, retain the “best and brightest” students, and promote economic and community development (THEC, 2021). We analyze seven TELS-funded programs, including the suite of four HOPE programs, the state’s broad-based merit aid program.

In 2013, Governor Bill Haslam launched *Drive to 55*, a statewide college completion initiative aimed at helping the state meet workforce development needs and boost economic development (Tennessee Department of Education, n.d.). The suite of universal aid programs growing out of *Drive to 55* (Promise, Reconnect, TCAT Reconnect) provide tuition-free community and technical college for eligible students and are aimed at helping students complete a community or technical college credential. Loan forgiveness programs tied to specific workforce sectors are another component of Tennessee’s aid system. The programs function as grant aid to be forgiven unless the service obligation goes unfulfilled. The state also operates other, often smaller programs, such as the merit-based Ned McWherter Scholars program and the STEP UP program, which provides aid to high school graduates with intellectual disabilities.

Data Collection

We collected data on the eligibility requirements and application process for 23 Tennessee aid programs from 2011 to 2024 by reviewing state administrative code, student aid commission documentation, and program websites, using the Internet Archive Wayback Machine and Thomson Reuters Westlaw database to locate information tied to the Tennessee Higher Education Commission (THEC) and Tennessee Student Assistance Corporation (TSAC). We drew on both administrative code and THEC and TSAC documents to learn about the process of applying for aid under each program because the state legislature established the programs in administrative code, and TSAC (which is part of THEC) administers aid programs. Drawing on both sets of documentation allowed us to capture information regarding requirements that legislators put into place when designing programs (which included program requirements, such as restrictions on institutions where students can enroll, citizenship and/or residency requirements, FAFSA submission) as well as requirements that TSAC put into place when implementing programs (which often outlined application logistics, such as deadlines, forms, and other requirements). Both sets of documentation helped us understand the complete set of program requirements, application logistics, documentation, and enrollment logistics for each program.

For each program, we collected data on 27 program features, drawing on the administrative burden framework from Rosinger et al. (2021) that identified features of aid programs that are likely to impose administrative burdens when students initially apply for aid (e.g., deadlines, program applications, documentation to verify grades and/or income, enrollment after high school, or full-time enrollment). To the list of program features developed by Rosinger and colleagues (2021), we iteratively added features that were specific to programs in our study

as we began our coding process, such as essay or recommendation requirements and whether a program awarded aid on a first-come, first-served basis. In doing so, our data collection sought to capture the learning and compliance costs associated with applying for each aid program by documenting the process of assessing program requirements and how to apply (learning costs) and complying with various program requirements (compliance costs).

Most of the program features we coded for likely impose both learning and compliance costs. For example, the program requirements listed in Table 2, such as residency, citizenship, or FAFSA requirement, impose learning costs as students learn about the program and assess the application logistics and compliance costs associated with satisfying these requirements. Many features could also impose psychological costs, such as stress associated with complying with program requirements or meeting certain requirements. Table 2 shows the complete list of data elements we collected for each program. In our dataset, we coded 1 for the presence of a particular program feature, or burden, and 0 for its absence. Together, the 27 data elements represent a comprehensive list of the program requirements, application logistics, documentation requirements, and enrollment logistics students need to meet in order to receive aid under each program.

[Table 2 Here]

Separate from data on administrative burden, we collected information regarding the target population(s) of each program to examine whether the social constructions of the targeted population related to different levels of administrative burdens. To do this, we examined the eligibility restrictions to understand whether each program was targeted toward a relatively advantaged and politically powerful group identified earlier (i.e., students meeting a specified academic threshold, students at four-year colleges) or a relatively less advantaged and less

politically powerful group (e.g., students with financial need, racially minoritized students, technical or community college students).

For each program, we coded variables indicating the target population as 1 if the program focused on that particular group (e.g., students with financial need) and 0 otherwise. We also collected data on the average aid award for each program in each year it operated (adjusted to 2023 dollars) since states might apply different levels of burden for larger versus smaller awards. In our analytic models, we adjust for average award amount to explore the relationship between administrative burden and a program's targeted population, independent of how large the award is. We gathered this data from the NASSGAP annual survey (<https://www.nassgapsurvey.com>), using data from THEC annual reports for programs or years for which NASSGAP data were unavailable.

We began data collection with one research team member coding for the presence or absence of each design feature for all programs. After this initial data collection, a second team member reviewed the coding and policy documents to determine whether the initial coder and the other team member agreed on the interpretation of policy documents and coding decisions. If there were discrepancies after the second review, both team members reviewed documents again to come to a final consensus. During data collection, members of the research team regularly discussed coding to ensure consistency. State officials at THEC provided information on program elements that we were not able to locate through our search of administrative code and program websites. In a very small number of instances, we were unable to find or verify documentation of a particular feature in a given year, and we used information from the two surrounding years to fill in missing data if requirements were the same in the years for which we had data.

Data Analysis

We used the 27 data elements we collected for each program to create an administrative burden index (ABI) that equaled the number of program features that existed in a given program in a given year, following the Rosinger et al. (2021) construction of an ABI for free college programs. This index is a measure of the level of administrative burdens a program imposes (or the number of tasks a student must complete and requirements they must meet to access aid), with a higher index value indicating more administrative burden (or more tasks and requirements). The ABI did not include basic eligibility requirements for programs that overlapped with target populations. For instance, ABI did not include whether a program was means-tested or whether a program included an initial academic requirement since these were basic eligibility requirements for need- and merit-based aid, respectively. As a result, the ABI represents the additional steps and requirements that eligible populations of students have for a particular program. For example, the ABI for the Tennessee Student Assistance Award, the state's primary need-based aid program, is a measure of the steps and requirements that students who qualify for need-based aid have to complete to receive the award. Similarly, the ABI for the HOPE Foster Child Grant represents the additional steps and requirements that former foster students need to complete to receive the award.

We used the ABI to answer the first two research questions, descriptively examining variation in ABI across programs in their most recent year (RQ1) and variation in ABI within programs over time (RQ2). We also examined which program features that likely contribute to administrative burdens were more and less common across aid programs over time.

To examine how the level of administrative burden in aid programs related to their target population (RQ3), we coded programs based on features of their targeted populations. We

created three binary variables indicating whether an aid program targeted relatively less-advantaged students. These included 1) students with financial need (i.e., need-based aid), 2) racially minoritized students, and 3) only students at technical and community colleges. We also created two binary variables indicating whether a program targeted relatively more-advantaged students. These included 1) students meeting academic thresholds (i.e., merit-based aid) and 2) only students at four-year universities.

To investigate whether aid programs imposed different levels of administrative burden depending on characteristics of targeted populations, we used a random effects estimator with the full panel of data (2011-2024) for each binary indicator to predict the ABI. The random effects equation can be expressed:

$$Y_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 TARGETPOP_{it} + \beta_2 AVGAWARD_{it} + T_t + (u_i + v_{it})$$

where Y_{it} is the ABI for a given program in a given year; $TARGETPOP_{it}$ is the binary variable indicating whether a program targeted a given population in a given year; $AVGAWARD_{it}$ is the average aid award for the program in a given year; T_t are year fixed effects; and $u_i + v_{it}$ is the composite error term.

In econometric approaches to panel data analysis, fixed effects estimators are often preferred because they likely produce less biased estimates by adjusting for individual program heterogeneity; however, to do so, the fixed effect absorbs any time-invariant characteristics of a program (which in this case would include the target population, the parameter we are interested in) (Wooldridge, 2009). As a result, we are unable to estimate a fixed effects model (since the target population is absorbed by the fixed effect) and so we rely on a random effects estimator, which allows us to examine the relationship between a target population and the program's ABI. Since this may lead to biased estimates (Wooldridge, 2009), we also estimated cross-sectional

models using one year of data (2024, or the most recent year a program operated). Results were consistent across cross-sectional and panel data models, except that we had less power to detect significant differences in burden level in the cross-sectional models. In addition, given that we estimate models for different target populations using the same dataset, we focus on findings that are significant at the .01 level to reduce the likelihood of a Type I error.

While the current study uses a blunt measure to indicate the presence of administrative burden (indicating whether a specific burden is present or not), we recognize some program features may be more onerous than others because they require a more sustained effort (e.g., enrolling in college full-time or maintaining continuous enrollment may impose a larger burden on students than completing FAFSA). We conducted a sensitivity check in which we weighted program features that require a more sustained effort as twice as burdensome than features that required less sustained effort (e.g., discrete tasks that could be completed in a couple of days, such as submitting FAFSA or standardized test scores). We then used this weighted index to examine variation in administrative burden across programs and in relation to targeted populations. Results were similar to those presented and are shown in Appendix C and D.

Findings

Figure 1 shows the ABI for each of the 23 Tennessee aid programs we examined. ABIs are shown for the most recent year, which was 2024 for all except six programs that ended operation prior to 2024.² The average program in its most recent year of operation had an ABI of 11.3 with a range of 8 to 15. The ABI can be interpreted as the number of program requirements, application logistics, documentation requirements, and enrollment logistics a student must complete to receive an initial aid award and can be examined alongside the average ABI across programs to investigate whether a program is relatively more (or less) burdensome than the

average aid program in Tennessee. The TSAA, the state’s largest need-based aid program (ABI: 8), the Community College Reconnect Grant (ABI: 9) and Wilder-Naifeh Technical Skills Grant (ABI: 9), which are targeted toward students at community and technical colleges, respectively, have low levels of administrative burden relative to other programs. By contrast, the Teaching Scholars program, the Future Teachers Scholarship, and the Minority Teaching Fellows program (all ABI: 15)—the only program that explicitly directs funds to racially minoritized students—had the highest levels of administrative burden.

[Figure 1 Here]

Interestingly, programs grouped together across a larger suite of programs (e.g., the suite of TELS programs, encompassing HOPE, HOPE Access, HOPE Non-Traditional, HOPE Foster Child, Aspire, and the General Assembly Merit Scholarship) varied in administrative burdens. TELS programs, which provide aid based on academic merit or a combination of need and merit, had ABIs ranging from 9 for its non-traditional student program, 10 for its foster child program, 11 for HOPE Access and HOPE Aspire (both targeted toward first-year students with financial need and academic merit), 11 for the General Assembly Merit Scholarship (targeted toward students with academic merit), and 12 for the HOPE program for first-year students. The state’s free college programs targeted toward adult students, TCAT Reconnect and Reconnect, had ABIs of 11, while Promise, which focuses on students enrolling in college shortly after high school graduation, had an ABI of 14.

Figure 2 shows the ABI for each of the 23 programs during the years they operated from 2011 to 2024. We find that programs’ level of administrative burden varied little over time: just three programs altered program requirements, application logistics, documentation requirements, and enrollment logistics in ways that likely made them more difficult to access. The Tennessee

Student Assistance Award, TCAT Reconnect, and Wilder-Naifeh Technical Skills Grant all added a deadline and the latter two began to encourage students to apply early. With these exceptions, ABI remained stable within programs over time until the pandemic period.

While the majority of the state's aid programs saw no changes to application requirements or logistics during the COVID-19 pandemic, the state made several specific changes related to Tennessee Promise and Tennessee Reconnect beginning in Spring 2020. Both programs saw enrollment policy change to allow less than continuous enrollment through the Summer 2021 term. The FY21 deadline for FAFSA submission was extended from February to May 2021 for Reconnect, while Promise saw its general FY21 application deadline extended by a month from November to December 2020. Finally, Tennessee Promise waived its community service requirement through the Summer 2021 term. The state also suspended requirements across all aid programs that placed time limits on when a student had to earn a qualifying exam score for enrollment in the Fall 2020 semester, but the requirement to submit a score remained. Each amended requirement has since been reinstated in its original form with the start of FY22.

[Figure 2 Here]

We also examined which features were most and least common across programs over time. Figure 3 is a heat map showing the share of programs with each administrative burden in a given year. Several requirements or burdens showed up across all programs each year they operated (shown in dark purple): recipients were required to be residents of Tennessee, U.S. citizens or eligible non-citizens, and not incarcerated. Other common aid requirements, represented by darker blue and purple cells (present in more than half of programs), included continuous college enrollment, program application, additional academic thresholds (beyond a basic eligibility criteria for merit-based aid), deadlines, awarding aid on a first-come, first-served

basis or otherwise encouraging an early application, restricting the institutions where funds could be used (usually for-profit institutions), and not having defaulted on educational loans. None of the programs required a drug test, criminal history reporting beyond that required for federal aid, confirmation of a code of conduct, specific high school curriculum, or campus-specific processes (shown by the yellow cells). Few programs required essays and/or recommendations (both of which were required for the Minority Teaching Fellows), volunteer requirements (required for Promise), or requirements to live in the state after the award (required for loan forgiveness programs) (shown in light green).

[Figure 3 Here]

Table 3 shows results from the series of random effects regressions using indicators of targeted populations to predict ABI. We found that the ABI for programs targeted toward students with financial need was not statistically different from non-need-based aid programs at the .01 level. That is, aid targeted toward students with financial need was not more (or less) onerous on average than programs that did not include means-tested requirements. The Minority Teaching Fellows program had a significantly higher ABI than programs that did not focus on racially minoritized students (by nearly 5 index points). Since this finding relied on comparing one program to all other programs and ABI was relatively stable over time, we also compared means over the sample period to see if descriptive results align with potentially less reliable model-based results: the Minority Teaching Fellows program had an average ABI of 15.79 over the period while all other programs had an average ABI of 10.78 over the period, which aligns with the random effects regression results. Programs targeted toward students at technical and community colleges had a statistically significant lower ABI (by around 2 index points) than programs targeted toward the four-year sector or across sectors. We found that programs targeted

toward relatively more-advantaged students (students who met merit-based criteria and students at four-year colleges and universities) did not have statistically different burdens from other programs.

[Table 3 Here]

Discussion

This study contributes to research examining administrative burdens in state aid programs (e.g., Bell et al., 2020; Bell & Smith, 2022; Rosinger et al., 2021; Steel et al., 2021) by considering how administrative burdens vary across programs within a state and how the targeted populations of programs relate to administrative burdens. We find that administrative burdens vary across programs in Tennessee but change little over time, showing the importance of policymaker and aid commission decisions in designing and implementing programs. Even during the pandemic, the state made some adjustments to reduce administrative burden, such as removing volunteer and continuous enrollment requirements, but other adjustments did little to alter the ultimate burden. For example, Tennessee's deadline for students to take the SAT or ACT was extended but the requirement remained, even while many institutions went test-optional for admissions (Rosinger, 2020).

In addition, we show that programs directed toward technical and community college students, who disproportionately come from racially and economically underserved backgrounds (Bailey et al., 2015), are associated with lower levels of administrative burden than other programs. These findings contrast with our initial hypotheses that programs targeting less-advantaged students would have more features that contribute to administrative burden than programs targeted toward more-advantaged students. So what could explain these contrasting results? We alternatively hypothesized that aid programs targeted toward technical and

community college students could be designed in ways that make aid easier to access. Therefore, although students themselves may wield little political power, technical and community colleges' close linkages to state workforce development goals and college completion initiatives may appeal to policymakers seeking support from industry.

State policymakers may therefore design these programs to be easier to access in an effort to increase college enrollment and make progress on college completion goals, such as Tennessee's *Drive to 55* initiative. After all, policymakers construct administrative burdens and can choose to reduce burdens in programs they support (Herd & Moynihan, 2018), such as ones that are closely linked with state goals. Further, the importance of technical and community college students in attaining state goals may mean these groups are more positively constructed in policymakers' and the public's perception, which is then reflected in policy design through average levels of administrative burden. In addition, if the targeted population of aid targeted toward technical and community college students is the institutions themselves, policymakers may perceive them as politically powerful and seek to gain support through easy-to-access funds that promote workforce development.

Our findings, however, do not directly contradict the idea that policymakers may impose higher levels of administrative burden in programs that target less-advantaged or less politically powerful students. In particular, the Minority Teaching Fellows program (the only program explicitly focused on racially minoritized students) imposed one of the highest levels of administrative burden on students. While the Minority Teaching Fellows and the Teaching Scholars Program both had relatively high burden, the first includes additional requirements that applicants of the latter program do not have to provide (applicants to both programs must submit a letter of recommendation, but Minority Teaching Fellow applicants must submit a second

reference and an essay). More broadly, it is important to also note the contrast in burdens between the teaching-focused programs (highest levels of burden across three teaching-focused awards), where workforce needs are high, and programs enacted under the *Drive to 55* initiative (lower levels of burden) that are aligned explicitly toward workforce needs.

Findings regarding aid programs targeted toward relatively less-advantaged students align to some extent with the idea that policy design reflects the social constructions of target populations—the extent to which populations are positively or negatively constructed and therefore deserving of aid or not and the extent to which populations wield political power (Schneider & Ingram, 1993). But the findings also show that in some cases, in particular when funding is directed toward students at technical and community colleges that are closely connected to workforce development, policymakers may design aid to be easier to access.

In contrast to our expectations, programs targeted toward relatively advantaged, positively constructed, and more politically powerful groups—students meeting academic thresholds and students at four-year colleges and their families—were found to encounter similar levels of burden as other programs. However, we highlight one additional implication regarding analyses concerning aid programs targeted toward technical and community college students: while these programs had lower administrative burden on average, the alternative interpretation indicates that other programs—those targeted to students across sectors and students at four-year colleges and universities—have higher levels of administrative burdens. This may reproduce inequities by posing one more barrier to high-achieving, underserved students receiving aid that can be used in the four-year sector. Thus, we find that administrative burdens may still serve as a mechanism through which policymakers allocate resources—in this case, in the form of aid that can be used across sectors—to more-advantaged populations (Ingram et al., 2019).

Importantly, entire groups of disadvantaged students are excluded from state financial aid in Tennessee: people who are currently incarcerated and undocumented students are not eligible for state aid programs in the state. These groups are often negatively constructed as undeserving of public programs and wield virtually no political power (Ingram et al., 2019). Schneider and Ingram (1993) note that policymakers may enact more coercive policies or sanctions toward groups that are negatively constructed and have little political power. While Tennessee has seen increasing levels of access to federal financial aid dollars for incarcerated students under the Second Chance Pell Program (Chesnut et al., 2022; Oakford et al., 2019), no such gains have been made for similar students seeking to access state-level aid. In Tennessee (and many other states (Custer & Akaeze, 2021)), state policymakers make state aid inaccessible to these students.

Contribution to Research and Future Research Directions

Complexity in federal financial aid deters some eligible students from receiving aid (Dynarski & Wiederspan, 2012). In response, researchers and organizations have developed individual-based interventions to help students navigate this complexity (e.g., Castleman & Page, 2016). Rather than nudging students to complete a complex process, other efforts have focused on systems, considering how aid programs themselves could be designed to reduce burdens, increase take-up, and promote more equitable outcomes. In recent years, policy efforts have resulted in several changes to simplify the federal aid process: a shortened FAFSA, an adjusted timeline that allows students to apply earlier using prior year tax returns, and linking tax returns directly to FAFSA (Dynarski & Wiederspan, 2012). Our study contributes to literature on financial aid complexity by demonstrating additional burdens policymakers place on students seeking state aid. It also contributes to our understanding of how financial aid programs and

decisions about how these programs are designed and implemented can reinforce (or interrupt) racial and economic inequities in college enrollment and completion.

We encourage researchers who study financial aid to focus on the broader systems that shape college enrollment and completion, for instance, through the burdens that programs impose on intended recipients. Such a focus would take the emphasis off of how students can be nudged to improve program uptake and turn the emphasis to how governments can design programs that better serve intended recipients. This approach would place problems at the feet of policymakers who design systems and policies rather than on individuals trying to navigate a complex system.

While our findings offer important insights into administrative burden in state aid and how it relates to the social construction of target populations, future research should allow for a more nuanced conceptualization of who is advantaged and who is not. Our study uses a blunt measure of “advantage” or “deservingness” by considering programs’ focus on financial need, academic merit, and institutional sector (though we would argue that policy actors frequently do the same in determining how to target aid). However, further exploration and refinement of “advantage” and “deservingness” (or lack thereof) is warranted since other states may ascribe different meanings to these concepts and therefore enact different levels of burdens during policy design. Future research can explore state policy documents to explore how deservingness is constructed for different groups of students at the state or more local level. For instance, if scholars find that West Virginia constructs different groups as deserving of state financial aid from Tennessee, this could help explain why it requires students who wish to use its free community college program to pass a drug test while Tennessee does not (Hazelrigg, 2019).

Our study is also limited by the inherent challenges of trying to quantify administrative burden since individual features of aid programs may impose different levels of administrative burden. Our sensitivity check along with prior research (Rosinger et al., 2021) has attempted to account for this by weighting program features that require longer-term efforts, such as maintaining a certain GPA, more than features that can be completed fairly quickly, such as signing a form. However, burdens affect individuals and groups in different ways. What may seem like a relatively small burden—signing a promissory note for loan forgiveness—can have psychological costs that are greater for some individuals and groups than others.

As a result, attempts to adjust weights attached to different program features may ignore their disproportionate effects on some intended recipients. While our findings were robust to models where we attached greater weight to program features that are likely to require more sustained effort, there are larger distinctions in burden across program features than a simple index can capture. Future research might investigate how individuals and groups navigate various burdens. Such work would identify specific burdens that are particularly onerous and offer insight into features policymakers could alter to design more equitable programs.

Finally, we focus on documenting the existence of and variation in administrative burdens within a single state over time. The evolution of aid programs in Tennessee follows broader national trends across states with an initial focus on need-based aid, the creation of a merit aid program, and the recent adoption of free college and other programs aimed at improving college completion and meeting workforce needs (Doyle, 2008; Mishory & Granville, 2019). The state has also served as a model for other state and federal aid programs (Finney et al., 2017). As such, it serves as an important case site in which to investigate administrative burdens that students face in accessing the state's aid programs. However, results may not be

generalizable to other states. States differ dramatically in the extent to which they offer financial aid and what types of programs they offer (NASSGAP, 2020; Rosinger et al., 2022). Future research might consider the extent to which these findings hold across other state contexts in order to offer more information to policymakers regarding a full range of program designs.

Subsequent research might also consider the impact of administrative burden across states on college enrollment and completion, particularly among low-income and racially minoritized students. Research might also investigate how the presence (or absence) of specific burdens shapes outcomes to understand which burdens are more or less inequitable. Such research would offer insights into the consequences of administrative burden.

Implications for Policy

Administrative burdens are the result of choices politicians and state officials make regarding policy design and implementation, and these choices have implications for whether and which individuals are able to access aid (Herd & Moynihan, 2018). In particular, administrative burdens can be racialized and serve to reproduce wider social inequities (Ray et al., 2022). But policymakers and state aid officials can make alternative choices, and this study offers several implications regarding the design and implementation of state aid programs. First, given the amount of variation that exists in administrative burden across programs in a single state, we recommend that state higher education officers and state policymakers consider the eligibility requirements and application process for each program to understand if, where, and why differences in administrative burdens exist. They may then identify some uncommon burdens (for example, the recommendation letters and essay required for Tennessee's Minority Teaching Fellows program) and examine the costs and benefits of these particular design

features. In addition, state policymakers should consider the benefits versus potential costs of any administrative burdens beyond those already imposed by FAFSA (which itself is a barrier).

Second, since many administrative burdens are written into state code and change little over time, as states introduce new programs or revise existing ones, they should carefully consider how additional requirements or complex application processes are likely to shape the outcomes of programs. In the coming years, changes to the federal aid application process may prompt state legislators and aid commissions to revise eligibility restrictions and program requirements to align with federal policy. These upcoming changes include revisions in how financial need is calculated and eligibility restrictions (e.g., removal of requirement for male students to register with the Selective Service and expanding eligibility to incarcerated individuals and individuals with drug convictions) (Federal Student Aid, 2021). Although the initial rollout of a simplified FAFSA has been delayed and rocky during the 2023-2024 academic year (Turner, 2024), these federal changes offer a policy window for state policymakers and aid commissions to revisit program requirements. Tennessee and other states have already shown an interest in streamlining aid processes, posing another impetus for adjusting requirements to reduce administrative burdens. This policy window is additionally supported by a Biden administration executive order that encourages reducing administrative burden in federal programs (The White House, 2021).

Finally, state policymakers may look at programs with closer linkages to workforce training, which our findings indicate tend to have lower burdens, in designing other programs. If policymakers continue to create similarly burdensome requirements for merit aid or programs that can be used across sectors, they may reproduce inequities in access to the four-year sector.

Our study extends prior literature on federal aid complexity by documenting complexity that exists in state aid programs in Tennessee, a state that has served as a model for many other state aid programs, and how this complexity relates to the target populations of these aid programs. Our findings highlight the need for policymakers to consider financial aid simplification at not only the federal level but at the state level as well.

¹ These included two state-level tuition assistance benefit programs, one federal loan forgiveness program, two programs that provide aid to high school students, and one state-administered federal program (see Appendix B for a list of excluded programs).

² We used 2013 data for Rural Health Loan Forgiveness, 2018 data for Community College Reconnect, 2020 data for the McAuliffe Scholarship, and 2021 data for the HOPE Access, Math and Science Teacher Loan Forgiveness, and Teaching Scholars programs since that was the last year each program operated.

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Table 1. Key features of state financial aid programs in Tennessee

Program	Sector	Target population	Award amount ^a	Need or academic requirement	Need threshold	Academic requirement	First-come, first-served ^b	Last dollar ^c	Additional documents	Deadline
Tennessee HOPE	Public 4-year Public 2-year Private	First-year students enrolling within 16 months of HS graduation	4yr Fresh/Soph: \$2,250 4yr Jun/Sen: \$2,850 2yr: \$1,600	Merit	N/A	21 ACT or 3.0 GPA	Yes	No	Yes	Sept. 1
Tennessee HOPE Access ^d	Public 4-year Public 2-year Private	First-year students enrolling within 16 months of HS graduation	4yr: \$1,250 2yr: \$875	Both	\$36,000	2.75-2.99 GPA and 18-20 ACT	Yes	No	Yes	Sept. 1
Tennessee HOPE Non-Traditional	Public 4-year Public 2-year Private	Students 25 and older who have not been enrolled for >2 years	Fresh/Soph: \$2,250 Jun/Sen: \$2,850	Both	\$36,000	2.75 GPA after 12 attempted hours	Yes	No	No	Sept. 1
Tennessee HOPE Foster Child Tuition Grant	Public 4-year Public 2-year Private	Foster children who meet TN Dept. of Children Services eligibility	\$6,012	Merit	N/A	Must meet for HOPE or HOPE Access requirements	No	No	Yes	N/A
Tennessee HOPE Aspire Award	Public 4-year Public 2-year Private	First-year students enrolling within 16 months of HS graduation	4yr: \$750 2yr: 250	Both	\$36,000	21 ACT or 3.0 GPA	Yes	No	Yes	Sept. 1
General Assembly Merit Scholarship	Public 4-year Public 2-year Private	First-year students enrolling within 16 months of HS graduation	\$500 per semester	Merit	N/A	3.75 GPA and 29 ACT	Yes	No	Yes	Sept. 1
Tennessee Promise	Public 4-year Public 2-year Private TCAT	First-year students enrolling within 16 months of HS graduation	\$2,074	Need	N/A	N/A	No	Yes	No	Promise: Nov. 1 FAFSA: Feb. 1
Tennessee Reconnect	Public 4-year Public 2-year Private TCAT	Independent adult students who have not earned a degree	Unknown	N/A	N/A	N/A	No	Yes	Yes	Sept. 1
TCAT Reconnect	TCAT	Adult students at a TCAT	\$1,285	N/A	N/A	N/A	No	Yes	No	July 1
Community College Reconnect Grant ^e	Public 2-year	Adult students returning to	\$1,994	N/A	N/A	N/A	Yes	Yes	No	N/A

Tennessee Student Assistance Award	Public 4-year Public 2-Year Private Proprietary TCAT	complete associate degree Students with financial need	4yr Public: \$2,000 2yr Public: \$2,000 Career: \$2,000 TCATS: \$2,000 4yr/4yr Private: \$4,000	Need	\$2,100	N/A	Yes	No	No	Feb. 1
Ned McWherter Scholars	Public 4-year Public 2-year	High school graduates	\$6,000	Merit	N/A	3.5 GPA and 29 ACT	Yes	No	Yes	Feb. 15
Tennessee STEP UP	Public 4-year Private	High school graduates with intellectual disabilities	Fresh/Soph: \$1,750 Jun/Sen: \$2,250	N/A	N/A	N/A	No	No	Yes	Sept. 1
Wilder-Naifeh Technical Skills Grant	TCAT	Students at a TCAT	\$2,000	N/A	N/A	N/A	No	No	No	Nov. 1
McAuliffe Scholarship ^f	Public 4-year Public 2-year Private Proprietary TCAT	Students in 3 rd year of approved teacher education program	\$594	Merit	N/A	3.5 GPA and ACT score >national average	Yes	No	Yes	N/A
Dependent Children Scholarship	Public 4-year Public 2-year Private Proprietary TCAT	TN residents who are dependent children of TN law enforcement, fireman, or EMT	\$12,001	N/A	N/A	N/A	Yes	No	Yes	July 15
Helping Heroes Grant	Public 4-year Public 2-year Private	TN veterans or the armed forces or former/current members of TN National Guard	\$1,000	N/A	N/A	N/A	No	No	Yes	Sept. 1
Tennessee Future Teachers Scholarship ^g	Public 4-year Private	College juniors and seniors enrolled in approved education preparation programs	Unknown	Merit	N/A	3.0 GPA or 21 ACT	No	Yes	Yes	Sept. 1

Minority Teaching Fellows	Public 4-year Public 2-year	Racially minoritized students in approved teacher education program in the state	\$5,000	Merit	N/A	2.75 GPA and 18 ACT, or top 25% of HS graduating class	Yes	No	Yes	April 15
Tennessee Teaching Scholars ^d	Public 4-year Public 2-year	Students admitted to approved teacher education program in the state	Unknown	Merit	N/A	2.75 GPA	Yes	No	Yes	April 15
Graduate Nursing Loan Forgiveness Program ^h	Public 4-year Public 2-year Private	Registered nurses seeking to become teachers and administrators in nursing education programs	\$7,000	N/A	N/A	N/A	Yes	No	Yes	March 1
Tennessee Math & Science Teacher Loan Forgiveness ^{dh}	Public 4-year Public 2-year Private	Public school teachers seeking advanced degree or certification in math or science in the state	\$2,000	N/A	N/A	N/A	No	No	No	Sept. 1
Tennessee Rural Health Loan Forgiveness ^{hi}	Public 4-year Public 2-year Private	Health care providers and dentists in the state	\$15,984	N/A	N/A	GPA and program test scores	No	No	Yes	Sept. 1

Notes. Data comes from academic year 2023-2024 unless indicated otherwise. Unless otherwise noted, academic requirement is for incoming first-year students.

^a Data on aid award amounts stems from program documentation in academic year 2023-2024 where available. For programs where award amounts are not publicized, or for programs that ceased operation prior to AY24, an average award amount was calculated using NASSGAP data from the most recent year of data collection, or the most recent year the program operated (adjusted to fiscal year 2024 dollars).

^b First-come, first-served indicates that aid is awarded on first-come, first-served basis and is coded as 1 if documents indicated there is a priority deadline, that the program might run out of money, or otherwise encourages students to apply early.

^c Last dollar indicates that program aid is awarded after any other grant aid funds a student receives are applied to tuition and fees. Unless documents explicitly noted that a program operated as a last-dollar program, we coded the program as first dollar.

^d Ceased operation in summer 2021.

^e Ceased operation in summer 2018.

^f Ceased operation in summer 2020.

^g Eligibility requirements apply to currently enrolled college students and graduate students. Incoming freshmen are ineligible become to apply beginning in AY22.

^h Aid offered to graduate students only.

ⁱ Operated in academic years 2008-2013.

Table 2. Data elements used to construct administrative burden index

Type of burden	Variable	Definition
Program requirements	Institution restriction	1 if program stipulates funds cannot be used in specific institutional sectors; 0 otherwise
	Incarcerated student restriction	1 if program restricts incarcerated students from receiving program funds; 0 otherwise
	Undocumented student restriction	1 if program restricts undocumented students from receiving program funds; 0 otherwise
	Residency restriction	1 if program stipulates an in-state residency requirement; 0 otherwise
	FAFSA	1 if state aid application requires FAFSA submission; 0 otherwise
	Need restriction ^a	1 if there an income, EFC, or other means-tested requirement; 0 otherwise
	HS curriculum requirement	1 if program requires student to complete a certain number of high school credits or specified curriculum in high school to receive award; 0 otherwise
	Academic requirement ^a	1 if program stipulates high school or college GPA, test scores, or other academic requirement above SAP; 0 otherwise
Application logistics	Additional academic requirement	1 if program stipulates an additional academic requirement (test score, etc.); 0 otherwise
	Essay(s)	1 if program requires a personal essay as part of application materials; 0 otherwise
	Recommendation(s)	1 if program requires recommendation letters on behalf of student; 0 otherwise
	Deadline	1 if state-specific deadline to apply for aid; 0 otherwise
	First-come, first-served	1 if aid is awarded on first-come first-served basis (code as yes if state uses language like: priority deadline, we might run out of money, so apply early or otherwise encourages students to apply early); 0 otherwise
	Last dollar	1 if aid is awarded on a last-dollar basis; 0 otherwise
	Form required	1 if state financial aid or program application required (beyond FAFSA); 0 otherwise
Documentation requirements	Additional requirements or documentation	1 if aid application includes additional requirements or documentation; 0 otherwise
	Promissory note requirement	1 if program requires students to sign a promisory note; 0 otherwise
	Live in state after award requirement	1 if program requires students to live in state for specified period of time after receiving award and/or after completing degree/certificate; 0 otherwise
	Loan repayment	1 if program stipulates loan and/or debt requirements for state/federal education loans
	Drug test reporting	1 if program requires students to take a drug test; 0 otherwise
	Criminal history reporting	1 if program requires students to self-report any aspect of criminal history beyond standard FAFSA reporting; 0 otherwise
	Code of conduct	1 if program requires other code of conduct; 0 otherwise
Enrollment logistics	Full-time enrollment	1 if program requires full-time enrollment (12 credit hours per semester); 0 otherwise

Enrollment within specified time after HS graduation	1 if program requires college enrollment in specified time period after high school graduation (e.g., immediately, 1 year, 2 years, 3 years); 0 otherwise
Volunteer requirements	1 if program requires student to volunteer or do some type of community service in order to receive award; 0 otherwise
Campus-specific requirements	1 if there are campus-specific requirements, i.e., campus can impose separate criteria in addition to state; 0 otherwise
Field of study restriction	1 if program restricts student college enrollment in a field of study, program type, or enrollment in non-credit-bearing coursework; 0 otherwise
Continuous enrollment restriction	1 if program requires students to maintain continuous enrollment to maintain award, or if program include a time limit for aid that indicates an expectation of continuous enrollment; 0 otherwise
Mentoring requirement	1 if program requires students to undergo behavioral support programming to maintain aid; 0 if otherwise

^aElement is excluded from administrative burden index because it is part of the target population (e.g., students with financial need, students meeting an academic requirement).

Table 3. Random effects regression results (2011-2024)

Targeted population	Random effects results	List of program(s) targeted toward specific population
Students with financial need	-1.876 (0.888)	Student Assistance Award, HOPE Non-Traditional, HOPE Access, HOPE Aspire (n=4)
Racially minoritized students	4.737*** (0.411)	Minority Teacher Fellows (n=1)
Only students at technical and community colleges	-2.221** (0.734)	Community College Reconnect, TCAT Reconnect, Wilder-Naifeh Technical Skills Grant (n=3)
Students meeting specific academic thresholds	1.793 (0.829)	HOPE Access, HOPE Aspire, HOPE Foster Child, General Assembly Merit, HOPE, McAuliffe Scholarship, Ned McWherter Scholarship, Minority Teaching Fellows, HOPE Non-traditional, Future Teacher Scholarship, Teaching Scholars (n=11)
Only students at four-year universities	0.094 (0.203)	HOPE Non-traditional, STEP UP, Future Teacher Scholarship (n=3)
Number of observations	251	

Notes. Results come from separate regression models in which programs are coded as 1 if they are targeted toward the specific population of students and all other state aid programs in Tennessee are coded as 0 (referent group). All models control for average aid award (logged) and year fixed effects. The outcome is the level of administrative burden in a given program in a given year. Robust standard errors are clustered in parentheses.

** p<.01 *** p<.001

Figure 1. Administrative burden index for state aid programs in Tennessee in 2024

Notes. For 6 programs that were discontinued prior to 2024, we used the most recent year the program was active. These programs were the Rural Health Loan Forgiveness (2013), Community College Reconnect Grant (2018), McAuliffe Scholarship (2020), HOPE Access (2021), Math and Science Teacher Loan Forgiveness (2021), and Teaching Scholars (2021).

Figure 2. Administrative burdens in state aid programs in Tennessee, 2011-2024

Notes. Administrative burdens shown for years in which each program was active. The Future Teacher Scholarship was only active in 2024, so + indicates the administrative burden for the one year the program operated during the study period.

Appendix A: Tennessee State Financial Aid Program Descriptions

Tennessee COVID-19 Financial Aid Policies

The Tennessee Student Assistance Corporation (TSAC) implemented a variety of policy changes designed to ameliorate difficulties faced by students during the COVID-19 pandemic. While the program overviews provided below contain traditional financial aid eligibility requirements, we first review the policy changes that impacted specific Tennessee financial aid programs in academic years 2019-2020 and 2020-2021.

Tennessee Promise and Tennessee Reconnect Enrollment Levels

TSAC provided guidance regarding changes in enrollment (COE) and leaves of absence (LOA). Schools were encouraged to consider COVID-19 an extenuating circumstance as it related to a student's LOA or COE during the spring and summer terms of the 2019-2020 academic year. If their institutions chose to follow TSAC guidance, recipients of Tennessee Promise and Tennessee Reconnect awards were not required to submit an appeal if their enrollment at the beginning of the Spring/Summer terms was less than the required minimum number of credit hours. TSAC later extended that guidance to include the Fall, Spring, and Summer terms of the 2020-2021 academic year. Under TSAC guidance, Summer 2021 Promise and Reconnect recipients remained eligible for the program in Fall 2021, even if they were enrolled in less than the required minimum number of credit hours at the beginning of the Fall semester.

TSAC's guidance did not apply in situations where Tennessee Promise and Tennessee Reconnect students change enrollment status from full-time to less than full-time or from part-time to less than part-time during the semester. Under such circumstances, a student was required to submit an appeal.

Source: https://www.tn.gov/content/dam/tn/thec/covid-19/Enrollment%20Guidance_March%202021.pdf.

Explicit Financial Aid Deadline Extensions

Policy changes relevant to programs analyzed in the current study:

- 1) Fall 2020 Tennessee Promise application deadline was extended from November 2, 2020, to December 1, 2020.
- 2) AY21 FAFSA deadline for Tennessee Reconnect extended from Feb 1, 2021, to May 15, 2021.

Source: <https://www.tn.gov/content/dam/tn/thec/covid-19/Program%20Requirements%20Memo%20-%20201-29-21.pdf>

Changes to Tennessee Promise Eligibility Requirements

Tennessee Promise community service requirements were waived, e.g., the April 2020 service requirement was waived, which enabled students to remain eligible to enroll in Summer 2020. The requirement continued to be waived in Summer 2020, Fall 2020, and Spring 2021, which meant that Promise recipients could continue to enroll through the Summer 2021 semester and receive aid without having met the service requirement.

Source: <https://www.tn.gov/content/dam/tn/thec/covid-19/Program%20Requirements%20Memo%20-%20201-29-21.pdf>.

Qualifying ACT Exam Scores for Fall 2020

TSAC suspended requirements that limit when a student must earn a qualifying exam score, as well as what kind of ACT examinations a student could take to qualify for the HOPE Scholarship, GAMS, and the HOPE Access Grant. The waiver was effective for the Fall 2020 term.

Existing policy for these programs required students to earn the minimum qualifying ACT composite score on a scheduled national or state exam taken prior to beginning classes in their freshman year. TSAC suspended this policy to allow incoming freshmen students to qualify for these programs using a score on a national or state ACT exam taken any time during the Fall 2020 term.

Additionally, TSAC suspended its policy which prohibited the use of ACT “residual” exam scores for the purpose of qualifying for these programs. A student who qualifies for these programs using an ACT residual exam score may only receive program funding toward attendance at the institution that administered the exam. TSAC accepted qualifying scores on residual exams taken from March 19, 2020, through the last day of the institution’s Fall 2020 term.

These temporary policy changes applied to 2020 high school and homeschool graduates, as well as 2019 high school and homeschool graduates enrolling for the first time in the Fall 2020 within 16 months of graduation.

Source: <https://www.tn.gov/content/dam/tn/thec/covid-19/ACT%20Memo%20for%20Website%20July%2017%202020%20.pdf>.

Tennessee HOPE Financial Aid Programs

Tennessee’s HOPE financial aid programs are funded from the net proceeds of the Tennessee Education Lottery Scholarship program (hereafter referred to as TELS). TELS state administrative code sets forth general student eligibility requirements for all students who receive TELS-funded financial aid, regardless of the specific HOPE aid program.

The initial suite of HOPE Scholarship programs first became available to students enrolling at Tennessee postsecondary institutions in Fall 2004. The current study analyzed student eligibility requirements across four HOPE programs (HOPE, HOPE Access, the HOPE Non-Traditional

Scholarship, and the HOPE Foster Child Tuition Grant), alongside two supplemental HOPE programs: the Aspire Award and the General Assembly Merit Scholarship.

TELS code states that HOPE aid recipients shall:

- 1) Be a Tennessee citizen; and
- 2) Be a Tennessee resident pursuant to T.C.A § 49-8-104 [2016]; and
- 3) Make application for a TELS award by submitting the FAFSA or Renewal FAFSA as required by Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-19-.03 [2015]; and
- 4) Be admitted to and enrolled in eligible postsecondary institution; and
- 5) Comply with United States Selective Service System requirements; for registration, if such requirements are applicable to the student; and
- 6) Be in compliance with federal drug-free rules and laws for receiving financial assistance; and
- 7) Meet each qualification relating to the relevant TELS award and applicable to the student; and
- 8) Not be in default on a federal Title IV educational loan or Tennessee educational loan; and
- 9) Not owe a refund on a federal Title IV student financial aid program or a Tennessee financial aid program; and
- 10) Not be incarcerated. [Text taken from Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-19-.02, 2021.]

TELS financial aid programs provide support to students enrolled throughout the state’s public colleges, universities, or private colleges, across two- and four-year sectors, including Tennessee Colleges of Applied Technology (TCATs) (T.C.A § 49-4-902, 2022). TELS does not provide aid to students enrolled in proprietary institutions within the state.

Students apply for all TELS-funded programs by submitting the Free Application for Federal Student Aid (FAFSA). For the six HOPE and HOPE-adjacent aid programs analyzed in the current study, students enrolling in a Fall term must submit the FAFSA by September 1; Spring/Summer enrollments must submit the form by February 1. No additional application forms are required. All TELS funded-programs are coded as first-come, first-serve programs in our dataset because “early application is recommended” (Tennessee HOPE Scholarship, 2020).

Full-time enrollment is not stipulated for TELS aid recipients. However, receipt of aid does require continuous enrollment at the student’s eligible postsecondary institution of choice (Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-19-.02, 2021).

Additional student eligibility requirements are broken down by individual HOPE aid programs.

Tennessee HOPE

The Tennessee HOPE Scholarship (hereafter referred to as TN HOPE) provides merit-based financial aid to “entering freshmen who are enrolled at an eligible postsecondary institution within sixteen (16) months after graduating from an eligible Tennessee high school” (Tennessee HOPE Scholarship, 2020). Eligible postsecondary institutions include those public/private four-year and two-year institutions across the state, not including TCATs.

Award amounts vary depending on the type of postsecondary institution attended, as well as the timing of aid receipt. Award amounts change over time and the numbers provided below reflect award amounts from AY24. For entering freshmen beginning with Fall 2015 and thereafter:

- 1) Four-Year institutions and Two-Year institution with on-campus housing: Up to \$2,250 per full-time enrollment semester as a freshman and sophomore; then up to \$2,850 per full-time enrollment semester as a junior and senior; including summer.
- 2) Two-Year Institutions Up to \$1,600 per full-time enrollment semester as a freshman and sophomore; including summer. [Text taken from Tennessee HOPE Scholarship, 2023.]

Entering freshmen must meet the following TN HOPE eligibility criteria in addition to the TELS general eligibility requirements:

- 1) Have been a Tennessee resident for one year by September 1 of the application date. For students beginning spring and summer terms, residency determined by February 1 as of application date; and
- 2) Graduate from a TN eligible high school; and
- 3) Enroll in one of the Tennessee public colleges, universities, or private colleges; and
- 4) Achieve a minimum of a 21 ACT or a minimum of a 1060 SAT, exclusive of the essay and optional subject area battery tests (concordant equivalent score) OR overall minimum 3.0 grade point average;
 - a) Home School graduates – minimum 21 ACT exclusive of the essay and optional subject area battery tests
 - b) GED recipients – minimum 21 ACT exclusive of the essay and optional subject area battery tests and qualifying GED score (minimum average Revised GED score is 170)
 - c) HiSet recipients – minimum 21 ACT exclusive of the essay and optional subject area battery tests and qualifying HiSet score (minimum average HiSet score is 15;
- 5) ACT/SAT exams must be taken on a national test date or state test date and prior to the first day of college enrollment (the ACT Residual test is not accepted); and
- 6) Must enroll within 16 months following high school graduation at any postsecondary institutions. However, enrollment at an ineligible postsecondary institution during the 16 months will make the student permanently ineligible. [Text taken from Tennessee HOPE Scholarship, 2020.]

In academic year 2023-2024, the program website added language to specific that only courses that count towards a student's degree can be funded using a HOPE Scholarship (Tennessee HOPE Scholarship, 2022).

Tennessee HOPE Access

By providing a need-based supplement to the Tennessee HOPE Scholarship program, the Tennessee HOPE Access Grant (hereafter referred to as Access) provides a combination of merit- and need-based financial aid to eligible students in Tennessee. Eligible students must be enrolled in an eligible postsecondary institution no later than sixteen (16) months after graduating from high school (Tennessee HOPE Access Grant, 2020). Eligible postsecondary institutions include those public/private four-year and two-year institutions across the state, not including TCATs. TSAC ceased accepting new applications for HOPE Access after September 1, 2021.

Award amounts varied depending on the type of institution attended, as well as the timing of aid receipt. For students who first received HOPE in Fall 2009 through Summer 2015:

- 1) Four-Year Institution: Up to \$1,375 per full-time enrollment semester; including summer.
- 2) Two-Year Institutions: Up to \$875 per full-time enrollment semester; including summer. [Text taken from Tennessee HOPE Access Grant, 2020.]

For entering freshmen beginning with Fall 2015 and thereafter:

- 1) Four-Year Institutions: Up to \$1,250 per full-time enrollment semester; including summer.
- 2) Two-Year Institutions: Up to \$875 per full-time enrollment semester; including summer. [Text taken from Tennessee HOPE Access Grant, 2020.]

Students applying for Access funds must meet all general eligibility requirements for TELS-funded state scholarships. Other Access student eligibility requirements include:

- 1) Have been a Tennessee resident for one year by September 1 of the application date. For students beginning spring and summer terms, residency is determined by February 1 as of application date; and
- 2) Graduate from a TN eligible high school; and
- 3) Enroll in one of the Tennessee public colleges, universities, or private colleges; and
- 4) Entering freshmen must have a final high school GPA between 2.75-2.99 AND between an 18-20 ACT or between 960-1050 SAT, exclusive of the essay and optional subject area battery tests.
 - a) Because the final high school GPA and the composite test score on the ACT/SAT range must fall between a specific range in order to qualify for this grant, entering freshmen cannot also academically qualify for the TN HOPE Scholarships at the same time;
- 5) ACT/SAT exams must be taken on a national test date or state test date and prior to the first day of college enrollment after high school graduation. The ACT Residual test is not accepted; and
- 6) Be admitted to and enroll in an eligible postsecondary institution no later than sixteen months after graduation from an eligible high school. [Text taken from Tennessee HOPE Access Grant, 2020.]

Tennessee HOPE Non-Traditional

By providing a need-based supplement to the Tennessee HOPE Scholarship program, the Tennessee HOPE Non-Traditional Scholarship program (hereafter referred to as HOPE-Non) provides a combination of need- and merit-based age to non-traditional age students. The target population for HOPE-Non funds has changed over time:

- 1) AY11-AY21: awarded to students of at least 25 years of age who enroll in a baccalaureate degree program at an eligible four-year postsecondary institution on or after August 1, 2018, as wither an entering freshman or with at least two years after last attending any postsecondary institution; or enroll in a baccalaureate degree program at all eligible four-year postsecondary institution on or after August 1, 2018 while maintaining continuous enrollment following the completion of an associate degree as a TN Reconnect recipient. [Text taken from Tennessee HOPE Scholarship – Nontraditional, 2020.]
- 2) AY23: awarded to entering freshmen or students who have not been enrolled in any college for at least two years from the date of last enrollment. [Text taken from Tennessee HOPE Scholarship – Nontraditional, 2021.]

- 3) AY24: awarded to independent students as determined by the FAFSA application and who have enrolled in a baccalaureate degree program at an eligible four-year postsecondary institution. [Text taken from Tennessee HOPE Scholarship – Nontraditional, 2023.]

Eligible four-year postsecondary institutions include the public and not-for-profit private sectors.

Award amounts vary over time and by the type of postsecondary institution attended. The numbers provided below reflect award amounts from AY24. For entering freshmen beginning with Fall 2015 and thereafter:

- 1) Four-Year institutions and Two-Year institutions with on-campus housing: Up to \$2,250 per full-time enrollment semester as a freshman and sophomore; then up to \$2,850 per full-time enrollment semester as a junior and senior; including summer.
- 2) Two-year institutions: Up to \$1,500 per full-time enrollment semester as a freshman and sophomore; including summer. [Text taken from Tennessee HOPE Scholarship – Nontraditional, 2023.]

Students who apply for HOPE-Non funds are expected to meet all TELS general eligibility requirements. Additional student eligibility requirements specific to the HOPE-Non program include:

- 1) Have been a Tennessee resident for one year by September 1 of the application date. For students beginning spring and summer terms, residency determined by February 1 as of application date; and
- 2) Be at least 25 years of age and enroll in a baccalaureate degree program at an eligible four-year postsecondary institution on or after August 1, 2018, as either an entering freshman or with at least two (2) years after last attending any postsecondary institution; or,
 - a) Enroll in a baccalaureate degree program at an eligible four-year postsecondary institution on or after August 1, 2018 while maintaining continuous enrollment following the completion of an associate degree as a Tennessee Reconnect aid recipient;
- 3) Have an adjusted gross income of \$36,000 or less on IRS tax form; and
- 4) Be continuously enrolled at an eligible postsecondary institution in the fall and spring semesters and maintain satisfactory academic progress; and
- 5) Have a minimum cumulative GPA of 2.75 after 12 attempted semester hours or required GPA or subsequent benchmark. (Attempted hours and college grades prior to re-enrollment at an eligible postsecondary institution after at least a two-year break in enrollment are not considered.); and
- 6) Enroll in one of the Tennessee public colleges, universities, or private colleges. [Text taken from Tennessee HOPE Scholarship – Nontraditional, 2020.]

Unlike other HOPE financial aid programs, HOPE-Non does not impose a limit on aid eligibility after high school graduation. The program requires a minimum college GPA for those students over the age of 25 who re-enroll at an eligible postsecondary institution within two years of prior attendance, which we coded as an academic requirement that could potentially impose an administrative burden on the program's aid applicants (Tennessee HOPE Scholarship – Nontraditional, 2023).

Students who apply for and receive HOPE-Non aid are ineligible to apply for funds stemming from the TELS-funded Aspire Award or General Merit Assembly Scholarship (Tennessee HOPE Scholarship – Nontraditional, 2023).

Tennessee HOPE Foster Child Tuition Program

First providing aid in FY2006, the Tennessee HOPE Foster Child Tuition Program (hereafter referred to as Foster) offers financial aid to a targeted student population: foster children (T.C.A. § 49-4-933, 2006). A “foster child” is defined as one who was in the custody of the Tennessee Department of Children’s Services in the following capacities:

- 1) For at least one (1) year after reaching thirteen (13) years of age; or
- 2) For at least one (1) year after reaching thirteen (13) years of age and placed for adoption by the Department of Children’s Services or one of its adoption contract agencies and the adoption was finalized; or
- 3) For at least one (1) year and placed in permanent guardianship by the Department of Children’s Services after reaching thirteen (13) years of age. [Text taken from Tennessee HOPE Foster Child Tuition Program, 2023.]

We coded the Foster program as a merit-based program given the need for students to meet the high school requirements for the Tennessee HOPE and HOPE Access Grant programs. Requirements regarding a recipient’s age changes over time. The minimum age is 14 through FY22. In FY23 the age min lowers to 13, reflected in both the program webpage documentation and in the program’s administrative code (Tennessee HOPE Foster Child Tuition Grant Program, 2022).

Receipt of a TN HOPE Foster Tuition Grant is contingent upon the following:

- 1) Students must meet the high school requirements for the TN HOPE scholarship or TN HOPE Access Grant; and
- 2) Be admitted to an eligible postsecondary institution (academically qualifying for any of these award programs does not guarantee admission to an eligible postsecondary institution); and
- 3) Present TSAC with official certification from the Department of Children’s Services that the student meets the eligibility requirements for the Foster program. [Text taken from Tennessee HOPE Foster Child Tuition Program, 2023.]

Foster award amounts cover the cost of attendance less any gift aid with the total award not to exceed the cost of tuition and fees at an eligible postsecondary institution. Furthermore, the award shall not exceed the statewide average tuition and mandatory fees for a public four-year or two-year postsecondary institution (Tennessee HOPE Foster Child Tuition Grant Program, 2023). Eligible postsecondary institutions include those public/private four-year and two-year institutions across the state, not including TCATs.

Students are eligible to apply for Foster aid for a period of no more than four years after the date of graduation from high school. Renewal criteria states that satisfactory academic progress must be achieved and maintained over a period of six years from admittance to an eligible postsecondary institution, which indicates an expectation of continuous enrollment. Students are

able to enroll part-time or full-time (Tennessee HOPE Foster Child Tuition Grant Program, 2023).

Program webpages and administrative code make no mention of a requirement to submit the FAFSA as part of the Foster application. However, HOPE Foster recipients are required to meet regular HOPE eligibility requirements, which includes FAFSA submission.

Program application deadlines are unknown.

Aspire Award

The Aspire Award (hereafter referred to as Aspire) is awarded to “entering freshmen as a supplement to the TN HOPE Scholarship” (Aspire Award, 2020). Eligible students must enroll in an eligible postsecondary institution no later than sixteen months after graduating from high school. Eligible postsecondary institutions include those public/private four-year and two-year institutions across the state, not including TCATs.

Award amounts vary depending on the type of institution attended, as well as the timing of aid receipt. For students who first received HOPE in Fall 2009 through Summer 2015:

- 1) Four-Year institutions: Up to \$750 per semester as a supplement to the HOPE Scholarship; including summer.
- 2) Two-Year institutions: Up to \$750 per semester as a supplement to the HOPE scholarship; including summer. [Text taken from Aspire Award, 2020.]

For entering freshmen beginning with Fall 2015 and thereafter:

- 1) Four-Year institutions: Up to \$750 per semester as a supplement to the HOPE Scholarship; including summer.
- 2) Two-Year institutions: Up to \$250 per semester as a supplement to the HOPE Scholarship; including summer. [Text taken from Aspire Award, 2020.]

Recipients of Aspire funds are expected to meet all TELS-funded general eligibility requirements, plus “parents’ or independent student’s spouse’s adjusted gross income of \$36,000 or less IRS tax form” (Aspire Award, 2020).

A student eligible for both the Aspire Award and the General Merit Assembly Scholarship shall be awarded the Aspire Award but cannot simultaneously receive both awards.

General Assembly Merit Scholarship

The General Assembly Merit Scholarship (hereafter referred to as GAMS) provides merit-based aid “to entering freshmen as a supplement to the HOPE Scholarship program” (General Assembly Merit Scholarship, 2020). Eligible postsecondary institutions include public/private four-year and two-year institutions across the state, not including TCATs.

For students who first received HOPE aid in Fall 2009 and thereafter, GAMS provides award amounts up to \$500 per semester as a supplement to the HOPE Scholarship, including the summer term (General Assembly Merit Scholarship, 2023).

Recipients of GAMS aid are expected to meet all TN HOPE general eligibility requirements, including the time limit on aid eligibility after high school graduation (eligible students must be admitted to and enrolled in an eligible postsecondary institution no later than sixteen (16) months after graduating from high school). Other GAMS-specific student eligibility requirements include:

- 1) Students graduating from a Tennessee public school or category I, II, III private school must have a minimum 3.75 GPA AND 29 ACT or a minimum 1330 SAT, exclusive of the essay and optional subject area battery tests; and
- 2) ACT/SAT exams must be taken on national test date or state test date and prior to the first day of college enrollment after high school graduation. The ACT Residual test is not accepted; and
- 3) Students graduating from Homeschool programs (and non-category, I, II, & III Schools), in addition to meeting the HOPE scholarship requirements, and during the course of a homeschool program, must meet the minimum academic requirements to qualify for GAMS. [Text taken from General Assembly Merit Scholarship, 2020.]

A student eligible for both the Aspire Award and the General Merit Assembly Scholarship can be awarded the Aspire Award but cannot simultaneously receive both awards.

Tennessee Reconnect Aid Programs

Over time, the suite of Tennessee Reconnect aid programs has encompassed three different scholarship applications: the TCAT Reconnect Grant, the Community College Reconnect Grant, and Tennessee Reconnect.

TCAT Reconnect Grant

The Tennessee College of Applied Technology (TCAT) Reconnect Grant (hereafter referred to as TCAT Reconnect) was established via the Tennessee Promise Scholarship Act of 2014 (T.C.A. § 49-4-708, 2014). Per communications with a state contact, the statutory title of the program is “Wilder-Naifeh Reconnect Grant”, but in programmatic discussions the program is referred to as “TCAT Reconnect”. The name was shortened after its introduction in 2015 for communication purposes and administering the program. The Wilder-Naifeh title first appeared on the TN financial aid website in July 2015 (Wilder-Naifeh Reconnect Scholarship, 2015). By July 2016, website language was updated to reflect TCAT Reconnect nomenclature (TCAT Reconnect Scholarship, 2016).

TCAT Reconnect is designed for “students with a FAFSA status of independent” who are enrolled full-time at a TCAT campus (TCAT Reconnect Scholarship, 2020). TCAT Reconnect funds are restricted for use by students enrolled at TCAT institutions. The program does not delineate any merit- or need-based eligibility requirements, nor any combination thereof. TCAT Reconnect provides last-dollar financial aid packages: “award amount varies based on amount of

remaining tuition and mandatory fees after all other gift aid has first been applied” (TCAT Reconnect Scholarship, 2020).

The FAFSA is the only application form students are required to submit in pursuit of TCAT Reconnect funding. Eligibility requirements from FY16 encourage students to submit the FAFSA by January 1 (Wilder-Naifeh Reconnect Scholarship, 2015). In FY18, deadline requirements change: FAFSA applications must be received by July 1 for the Summer trimester, November 1 for the Fall trimester, and March 1 for the Winter/Spring trimester; application instructions are also amended to indicate that “early application is recommended” (TCAT Reconnect Scholarship, 2017).

TCAT Reconnect student eligibility requirements include:

- 1) Meet the requirements of §§ 49-4-904 [2003] and 49-4-905(a) [2020]; and
- 2) Be admitted to the institution in an eligible program of study; and
- 3) Complete and file the FAFSA; and
- 4) Be an independent student as determined by the FAFSA; and
- 5) Enroll full-time as defined in T.C.A. § 49-4-708 [2022]; and
- 6) Maintain continuous enrollment; and
- 7) Reapply annually to continue receiving funds; and
- 8) Grants may not be used for continuing education courses; and
- 9) No student shall be eligible for more than one (1) TCAT Reconnect grant at a time. [Text taken from T.C.A. § 49-4-923, 2021.]

Community College Reconnect Grant

Per communications with a state contact, the Tennessee Reconnect Grant program was originally established as the Community College Reconnect Grant (hereafter referred to as CCRG), and first provided aid to students enrolled for Fall 2015. CCRG terminates in Summer 2018, at which point active CCRG recipients who remained eligible for the award began participating in the newly announced Tennessee Reconnect Grant program.

CCRG provided last-dollar scholarship funds “to offset tuition and mandatory fees associated with pursuing an associate degree at an eligible postsecondary institution after all other gift aid has been credited to tuition and mandatory fees” (Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-27-.02, 2017). Returning adults must have previously completed a minimum of 30 credit hours and have not attended a postsecondary institution for at least 12 months prior to enrollment (Community College Reconnect Grant, 2017). The program does not delineate any merit- or need-based eligibility requirements, or any combination thereof. CCRG funds could be used across the state’s public two-year community college sector, not including TCATs.

Institutions “determine[d] eligible recipients based on a first-come, first-served methodology and the availability of funding” (Community College Reconnect Grant, 2017). Students applied to CCRG funds via FAFSA submission (deadlines included: September 1 (Fall) and February 1 (Spring/Summer)). No additional application forms were required.

Student eligibility requirements included:

- 1) Tennessee resident and a U.S. citizen, or eligible non-citizen; and
- 2) File the FAFSA by the deadline date; and
- 3) Be in pursuit of an associate degree; and
- 4) Have previously earned at least 30 hours toward an associate degree; and
- 5) Not enrolled in or attended any postsecondary institution for at least 12 months; and
- 6) Enroll in and attend at least nine (9) hours at a Tennessee community college; and
- 7) Maintain a minimum of 2.0 GPA and satisfactory academic progress. [Text taken from Community College Reconnect Grant, 2017.]

CCRG applicants were not required to provide any prior documentation of GPA or test scores from high school. The stipulation regarding nine-hour enrollment equates to a full-time enrollment requirement. Students were also required to remain continuously enrolled in order to continue receiving the award.

Tennessee Reconnect Grant Program

The Tennessee Reconnect Grant program (hereafter referred to as Reconnect) began operation in Fall 2018. Reconnect funds are available to “students who have not previously earned an associate or baccalaureate degree, are independent according to FAFSA rules, and are enrolled part-time in an eligible program of study” (Tennessee Reconnect Grant, 2020). The program does not delineate any merit- or need-based eligibility requirements, or any combination thereof. In academic year 2023-2024, the program introduced an age minimum: applicants must be classified as independent on the FAFSA or be at least 23 years of age by January 1 of the academic year they apply (Tennessee Reconnect Grant, 2023).

Prior to the availability of Reconnect funds in Fall 2018, students using CCRG funds were restricted to enrollment at community colleges, not including TCATs. Reconnect expanded the CCRG framework for students enrolled in associate degree programs across four-year, two-year, and private sectors, including (TCATs). Reconnect also made it possible for students to enroll in eligible two-year programs at eligible four-year colleges or universities.

Reconnect “award amounts vary based on the amount of remaining tuition and mandatory fees after all other gift aid has first been applied” (a last-dollar aid program) (Tennessee Reconnect Grant, 2020).

Generally, students must submit the FAFSA in order to apply for Reconnect funds: September 1 (Fall) and February 1 (Spring/Summer) (Tennessee Reconnect Grant, 2020). Students must also submit a separate Reconnect application via the Tennessee Student Assistance Corporation (TSAC) Portal. The program’s FAFSA deadline language does not appear on the program website in AY24. The AY24 webpage states the following: “File the FAFSA by the deadline date and be classified as an independent student OR be at least 23 years of age on or before January 1 of the academic year applied” (Tennessee Reconnect Grant, 2023). For this reason, we note the AY24 deadline as “unknown.”

Reconnect student eligibility requirements include:

- 1) Tennessee residency for one (1) year prior to date of application; and
- 2) File the FAFSA annually and be classified as an independent student; and
- 3) Be enrolled in a federal Title IV eligible curriculum of courses leading to a certificate or associate degree; and
- 4) Not have previously earned an associate degree or baccalaureate degree; and
- 5) Enroll in and attend at least six (6) hours at an eligible institution (continuous, part-time enrollment); and
- 6) Maintain a minimum 2.0 cumulative GPA at the end of the academic year as determined by the institution; and
- 7) Participate in a college success program, as determined by the Tennessee Higher Education Commission (THEC); and
- 8) Not be ineligible for the grant under T.C.A. 49-4-904. [Text taken from Tennessee Reconnect Grant, 2020.]

No explanatory details could be found regarding the program's requirement to participate in a "college success program" on either the program website or in the program's administrative code.

Coding for AY22 was imputed using comparison data from AY21 and AY23.

Tennessee Promise

The Tennessee Promise scholarship (hereafter referred to as Promise) began offering aid to students in the 2014-2015 academic year. Promise is available to "Tennessee residents, U.S. citizens, and eligible non-citizens who graduate from an eligible high school, homeschool, or earn a GED/HiSet prior to their nineteenth (19th) birthday" (Tennessee Promise Scholarship, 2020). The program does not delineate any merit- or need-based eligibility requirements, nor any combination thereof. Instead, promise provides "last-dollar financial aid, mentoring, and community service opportunities for Tennessee students" (Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-26-.01, 2019).

Promise funds can be used in two-year programs across the state's public four- and two-year sectors, including Tennessee Colleges of Applied Technology (TCATs) and private, non-profit technical schools (Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-26-.03, 2017). Students must be enrolled full-time in an eligible postsecondary institution in order to maintain eligibility for the program and continuous enrollment is expected except for approved medical or personal leaves of absence (Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-26-.04, 2019).

Promise is primarily coded as a last-dollar program. At four-year institutions, however, Promise does not function as a last-dollar program. The amount of Promise funding received for an associate degree program at a four-year institution will be based on the average amount of tuition and fees at a community college (T.C.A. § 49-4-708, 2022).

Promise aid recipients are required to attend mandatory meetings, participate in a mentoring program, and perform 8 hours of community service each term the award is received (Tennessee Promise Scholarship, 2020).

In academic year 2023-2024, applicants were required to submit a stand-alone Promise application by November 1 and submit the FAFSA by March 1 (Tennessee Promise Scholarship, 2023). Both respective deadlines have changed over time, with annual changes occurring from AY21-AY24.

Promise administrative code makes no mention of access to aid for incarcerated students or undocumented students. The code also lacks any reference to requirements regarding student loan repayment/default, as stipulated by other aid programs in the state.

Wilder-Naifeh Technical Skills Grant

The Wilder-Naifeh Technical Skills Grant (hereafter referred to as WNTS) was also established and funded from TELS net proceeds program alongside the suite of HOPE scholarship programs. WNTS is awarded to students who are enrolled at a TCAT. The program is available to “all students enrolled at a TCAT who have been Tennessee residents for one year prior to enrollment” (Wilder-Naifeh Technical Skills Grant, 2020). The program does not delineate any merit- or need-based eligibility requirements, nor any combination thereof. WNTS awards cover costs of attendance up to \$2,000.

Students apply for WNTS funds by submitting a FAFSA. Deadlines for application break down by the term enrolled: November 1 (Fall), March 1 (Winter/Spring); July 1 (Summer) (Wilder-Naifeh Technical Skills Grant, 2020). There is no time limit for applicants to apply for WNTS funds after high school graduation. No minimum number of enrollment hours are required for WNTS eligibility.

WNTS recipients are expected to meet TELS ineligibility requirements (T.C.A. § 49-4-904, 2003). Additional WNTS-specific student eligibility requirements include:

- 1) Enroll in a certificate or diploma program at a TCAT and maintain satisfactory academic progress and continuous enrollment; and
- 2) Cannot be a prior recipient of the Wilder-Naifeh Technical Skills Grant. [Text taken from Wilder-Naifeh Technical Skills Grant, 2020.]

WNTS grants may not be used for continuing education courses and students can only receive one (1) WNTS grant over time (T.C.A. § 49-4-921, 2022).

Tennessee Student Assistance Award

First established in 1974, the Tennessee Student Assistance Award program (hereafter referred to as TSAA) was designed to provide “non-repayable assistance to financially needy undergraduate students who are residents of Tennessee” (Tennessee Student Assistance Award, 2020). The TSAA is a first-dollar, need-based grant aid program, funded in part by TELS and (at one point) federal LEAP/SLEAP program (Tennessee Student Assistance Award, 2010).

From AY11 to AY21, the program’s need threshold is set at \$2,100 (Tennessee Student Assistance Award, 2020). Beginning in AY22, the expected family contribution annually,

currently sitting at \$5,846 in academic year 2023-2024 (Tennessee Student Assistance Award, 2023).

Maximum award amounts are determined by TSAC prior to the beginning of the fall term. The amount of the award is based on the institution indicated on the student's FAFSA. Award amounts depend on the type of institution attended [NOTE: numbers provided below reflect award amounts from FY24, which represents an increase in amount for two-year publics and TCAT campuses from prior years]:

- 1) Four-Year/Two-year private: \$4,000.
- 2) Four-Year public: \$2,000.
- 3) Two-Year public: \$2,000.
- 4) Career Schools: \$2,000.
- 5) Tennessee College of Applied Technology: \$2,000. [Text taken from Tennessee Student Assistance Award, 2023.]

Students apply for TSAA funds by submitting the FAFSA annually. In FY11, the TSAA website instructs students to submit their FAFSA as soon as possible after January 1, and includes a priority deadline of February 15 (Tennessee Student Assistance Award, 2010). Because these instructions do not impose a state-specific deadline after which students cannot apply for TSAA funds each year, the program deadline is coded as "0" for FY11-FY14. In FY12, the priority deadline language was removed from the TSAA website, though it still encourages students to apply as soon as possible after January 1 (Tennessee Student Assistance Award, 2011). The consistent "early application" language led us to code the program as first-come, first-serve.

In FY15, the TN state financial aid website introduced a new TSAA deadline component (Tennessee Student Assistance Award, 2014). The standard "apply as soon as possible after January 1" dictum remains in place. However, new language then states that prior-year recipients (renewals) will receive the award if they meet all eligibility requirements and complete the FAFSA on or before March 1. After March 1, remaining funds are awarded to the neediest applicants who apply by March 1 based on the availability of funds (awards to be made until funds are depleted). In FY18, the March 1 deadline became a January 17 deadline in response to the expanded FAFSA application window (Tennessee Student Assistance Award, 2017). This deadline changes again in FY20, to February 1 (Tennessee Student Assistance Award, 2019). From FY15-FY21, the deadline variable is coded "1". The priority deadline is noted for FY21 only.

The Tennessee Student Assistance Corporation (TSAC) administers the TSAA. TSAA promulgated rules do not include a time limit after graduating high school in which students must apply for TSAA. However, the TSAA website updates in FY14 to include the following stipulation: to be eligible, the applicant must not have already received a baccalaureate degree (Tennessee Student Assistance Award, 2013).

TSAA is historically one of only four state-funded aid programs over time to provide aid to all postsecondary educational sectors, including Tennessee Colleges of Applied Technology (TCATs) and proprietary institutions (T.C.A. § 49-4-301, 2021).

State administrative code dictates that incarcerated students are ineligible to receive TSAA funds and also states that students who are citizens of the United States shall receive priority, providing no alternative pathway for undocumented students to apply for TSAA funds (T.C.A. § 49-4-301, 2021).

Eligible students must not owe a refund or repayment on any grant, and not be in default on any loan, received at any institution under provisions of Title IV of the Higher Education Act of 1965 (Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-01-.02, 2015).

Tennessee STEP UP Scholarship

Effective May 2014, the Tennessee STEP UP Scholarship program (hereafter referred to as STEP UP) is “designed to assist students with intellectual disabilities who have completed high school and enroll in an individualized program of study of up to four (4) years at an eligible postsecondary institution” (Tennessee STEP UP Scholarship, 2020). The program does not delineate any merit- or need-based eligibility requirements, nor any combination thereof.

In FY15 and FY16, STEP students received \$2,000 in aid (Tennessee STEP UP Scholarship, 2014; Tennessee STEP UP Scholarship, 2015). Beginning in FY17, the program begins to differentiate award amounts by class distinction. Award amounts change over time, with numbers from FY24 presented below:

For entering students beginning with Fall 2015 and thereafter: Award amount is up to \$2,250 per full-time enrollment semester as a freshman and sophomore then up to \$2,850 per full-time enrollment semester as a junior and senior. [Text taken from Tennessee STEP UP Scholarship, 2023.]

STEP UP student eligibility requirements include:

- 1) Not be ineligible for the scholarship under T.C.A. § 49-4-904; and
- 2) Have been a Tennessee resident, as defined by regulations promulgated by the board of regents under § 49-8-104 [2016], for one (1) year immediately preceding the date of application for a scholarship or the renewal of the scholarship; and
- 3) Complete high school in a Tennessee high school in accordance with the requirements of the student’s Individualized Education Program (IEP) and receive a high school diploma, occupational diploma or certificate, a special education diploma, a transition certificate, or an IEP certificate; and
- 4) Be admitted to and enroll in an eligible postsecondary institution in an eligible postsecondary program no later than sixteen (16) months after completing high school; and
- 5) Apply for a Tennessee STEP UP Scholarship each academic year. [Text taken from Tennessee STEP UP Scholarship, 2020.]

For academic years 14-15, 15-16, and 16-17, STEP UP funds were restricted to “two-year individualized program(s) at an eligible postsecondary institution” (Tennessee STEP UP Scholarship, 2016). This meant that funds could be spent at four-year institutions, but only for enrollment in two-year academic programs. In AY18, however, the program language is updated to allow funds to be used in “an individualized program of study of up to four (4) years at an eligible postsecondary institution” (Tennessee STEP UP Scholarship, 2017). Through FY21, the defined list of eligible institutions and programs included Lipscomb University (IDEAL

Program), Union University (Union EDGE Program), University of Memphis (TigerLIFE), University of Tennessee (UT FUTURE), and Vanderbilt University (Next Steps) (Tennessee STEP UP Scholarship, 2020). In academic year 2023-2024, the program's list of eligible institutions was updated to include Dyersburg State Community College (Tennessee STEP UP Scholarship, 2023).

Students and parents must complete a stand-alone STEP UP scholarship application and email the completed form to STEP.program@tn.gov. In addition, recipients must complete the FAFSA each academic year. Both the STEP UP form and the FAFSA must be submitted by September 1 for Fall enrollment, February 1 for Spring enrollment, and May for Summer enrollment (Tennessee STEP UP Scholarship, 2020).

STEP UP recipients must maintain continuous enrollment in the eligible postsecondary program of choice, but the program does not require full-time enrollment (T.C.A. § 49-4-943, 2020).

STEP UP administrative code makes no mention of access to aid for incarcerated students or undocumented students.

Ned McWherter Scholars Program

First established in 1986, the Ned McWherter Scholars program (hereafter referred to as NMS) is “intended to encourage academically superior Tennessee high school graduates to attend college in Tennessee” Tennessee high school seniors starting their last semester in high school may apply” (Ned McWherter Scholars Program, 2020). State administrative code from 2002 stipulates that applicants must “be an applicant for initial admission to college after high school graduation at the time of his/her initial application for the scholarship” (Chapter 1640-01-09-.02, 2002). Code from 2017 reflects the following update: applicants must “enroll at an eligible postsecondary institution within sixteen months following graduating from high school” (Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-09-.02, 2017). We code the program as imposing a time limit for aid eligibility after high school graduation across all years in the dataset.

NMS provides merit-based financial aid awards of up to \$6,000 per academic year (\$3,000 from the State of Tennessee and \$3,000 from the college or university attended) (Ned McWherter Scholars Program, 2020).

While NMS does not require applicants to submit the FAFSA, students must submit a stand-alone NMS application via the Tennessee Student Assistance Corporation (TSAC) portal which must be submitted by February 15 each year, alongside copies of their high school transcripts (containing grades through the first semester of senior year) and official ACT/SAT scores (Ned McWherter Scholars Program, 2020).

We code NMS as a first-come, first-serve program because, “NMS awards are competitive and are based on limited funding” (Ned McWherter Scholars Program, 2020).

NMS-specific student eligibility requirements include:

- 1) Be a resident of Tennessee, a U.S. citizen or permanent resident, and attend an eligible Tennessee college or university full-time; and
- 2) Have at least a 3.5 unweighted grade point average; and
- 3) Have a minimum composite score of 29 on the ACT (or concordant equivalent score on the SAT). [Text taken from Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-09-.02, 2017.]

NMS funds may be used at public four- and two-year institutions but their use is prohibited at TCATs and proprietary institutions (Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-09-.03, 2017).

NMS administrative code names no mention of access to funds for incarcerated students or undocumented students, nor does the code stipulate and educational loan repayment/default requirements.

Christa McAuliffe Scholarship Program

Established in 1986, the Christa McAuliffe Scholarship program (hereafter referred to as CMSP) was created to “honor the memory of Christa McAuliffe, a high school teacher who lost her life in the space shuttle Challenger accident... [and was] designed to encourage promising Tennesseans who have a commitment to teaching and inspiring young minds to explore and achieve their highest potential” (Christa McAullife Scholarship Program, 2019). The program was terminated effective August 1, 2020 (T.C.A. § 49-4-705, 2020). There are alternate spellings of “McAuliffe” found across the program’s documentation. CMSP administrative code spells the name “McAuliffe” (Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-10-.01, 1986). The TN state financial website consistently spells the name “McAullife” (Christa McAullife Scholarship Program, 2019). CMSP was “intended to assist and support Tennessee residents who have demonstrated a commitment to a career in educating the youth of Tennessee” (Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-10-.01, 1986). The program ceased operation in Summer 2018.

CMSP administrative code from 2002 is attached as the “promulgated rules” document for AY11-FY17 on the TN state financial aid website (Christa McAullife Scholarship Program, 2016). The TN state financial aid website consistently communicated a one-time award amount of \$500 from FY11-FY20 (Christ McAullife Scholarship Program, 2019). However, all versions of the CMSP administrative code refer to a maximum award amount of \$1,000 (Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-10-.02, 1986).

According to a response from a state contact, there were no restrictions on the type of postsecondary institutions students can attend in receipt of CMSP funds. The state contact communicated that the program likely had less than 10 students total in the lifetime of the award. CMSP was one of only two state-funded grant programs within Tennessee that have provided aid to students across all postsecondary sectors over time, including TCATs and proprietary institutions. The Tennessee Student Assistance Award (TSAA) also provides aid to students across all institutional sectors.

In order to be eligible for CMSP funding, students must:

- 1) Be a rising college junior enrolled full-time in a teacher education program in an accredited Tennessee postsecondary institution; and

- 2) Have completed at least their first semester of their junior year; and
- 3) Have at least a 3.5 cumulative grade point average; and
- 4) Have an ACT or SAT score that meets or exceeds the national norm. [Text taken from Christa McAullife Scholarship Program, 2019.]

Students applied for CMSP funds via the TSAC online portal by April 1 each year, alongside official college transcripts and an official SAT/ACT score, with no requirement to submit the FAFSA (Christa McAullife Scholarship Program, 2019). We code CMSP as first-come, first-serve because CMSP funds were “very competitive and [were] based on limited funding” (Christa McAullife Scholarship Program, 2019).

CMSP administrative code states that students must be enrolled full-time within their approved teacher education program (Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-10-.04, 1992). While the code also required students to maintain a statement of compliance with federal drug-free rules and laws on file with their institution of choice; it makes no mention of loan repayment/default requirements typical of other aid programs in the state.

CMSP administrative code makes no mention of pathways to aid application for incarcerated students or undocumented students.

Helping Heroes Grant

Enacted by public necessity rule in October 2008, the Helping Heroes Grant was established and funded from the net proceeds of the state lottery (T.C.A. § 49-4-938, 2008). There is no need- or merit-based designation for this aid program. Instead, grants are awarded to U.S. veterans who were honorably discharged or who are a former or current member of a reserve or Tennessee National Guard Unit. Eligible veterans include those who have been awarded the Iraq campaign medal; the Afghanistan campaign medal; on or after September 11, 2001, the global war on terrorism expeditionary medal; or, a service expeditionary medal identified in rules and regulations promulgated by TSAC (T.C.A. § 49-4-938, 2008). Helping Heroes recipients are able to enroll in two-year and four-year institutions across the public and private sectors.

Receipt of a Helping Heroes Grant occurs after the completion of a semester. Students are awarded \$1000 per semester if they successfully complete twelve or more semester hours with no failing grade as the final grade for the course. Typically, students will receive \$500 per semester for successfully completing six to eleven semester hours with no failing grade as a final grade for the course. However, in academic year 2021-2022, the “failing grade” language was removed from the program webpage (Helping Heroes Grant, 2021). Part-time enrollment is required to receive a Helping Heroes Grant.

Helping Heroes is explicitly denoted as a first-come, first-serve grant program through academic year 2021-2022 (Helping Heroes Grant, 2021). In FY23, the first-come first-serve language disappears from program webpages (Helping Heroes Grant, 2022).

Program eligibility requirements include:

- 1) Be an honorably discharged veteran who had formally served the armed forces of the United States, or a former or current member of a reserve or TN National Guard unit who was called into active military service of the United States; and
- 2) Be a TN resident for one year preceding the date of application for the grant; and
- 3) Enroll at an eligible two-year or four-year postsecondary institution; and
- 4) Have not earned a baccalaureate degree; and
- 5) Not be in default on a federal Title IV educational loan or TN educational loan; and
- 6) Not owe a refund on a federal Title IV student financial aid program or a TN student financial aid program; and
- 7) Be in compliance with federal drug-free rules and laws for receiving financial assistance; and
- 8) Not be incarcerated; and
- 9) Meet each qualification relating to this grant and applicable to the student; and
- 10) Not be required to meet any academic standard at the time of enrollment in order to be eligible for this grant. [Text taken from Helping Heroes Grant, 2023.]

Deadlines to submit the Helping Heroes application include:

- 1) Fall enrollment: September 1
- 2) Spring enrollment: February 1
- 3) Summer enrollment: May 1

Students are required to email or fax the completed application and a completed DD-125 Form to TSAC.

A student's award will terminate under the following conditions:

- 1) After eight full semesters have passes; or
- 2) After the eighth anniversary of the veteran's honorable discharge from military service, whichever comes first; or
- 3) After earning a baccalaureate degree, whichever comes first. [Text taken from Helping Heroes Grant, 2023.]

While there is no explicit mention of continuous enrollment in the program eligibility requirements, the award termination criteria indicates that there is a time limit for aid receipt that encourages continuous enrollment in an effort to maintain progress towards a degree.

Dependent Children Scholarship

Established in 1990, the Dependent Children Scholarship Program (hereafter referred to as DCS) "provides aid for Tennessee residents who are dependent children of a Tennessee law enforcement officer, fireman, or an emergency medical service technician who has been killed or totally and permanently disabled while performing duties within the scope of such employment (T.C.A. § 49-4-704, 2009). The parent must be a Tennessee resident and have been on duty when the incident occurred" (Dependent Children Scholarship Program, 2022). The scholarship is awarded to full-time undergraduate students attending eligible TN institutions. Annual award amounts are subject to variations in state funding. There is no need- or merit-based component to the aid program. DCS recipients are able to enroll across all institutional types within the State of Tennessee.

The following definitions stem from T.C.A. § 49-4-704 (2009). “Dependent child” refers to a natural child, stepchild, or adopted child who is either living with or receiving regular support contributions from a law enforcement officer, firefighter, or emergency medical service technician at the time of the employee’s death or total and permanent disability. “Dependent child” can also refer to a posthumous child. “Emergency medical service technician” refers to an individual who possesses a valid certificate issued pursuant to Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 68-140. “Firefighter” is defined as in T.C.A § 4-24-201 or a bona fide member of a volunteer fire department. “Law enforcement officer” means any police officer of a TN municipality, any commissioned member of the department of safety, the wildlife resources agency, or the TN bureau of investigation, and any TN county sheriff or deputy sheriff actually engaged in law enforcement, or any correctional officer employed by the department of correction or the department of children’s services.

Website and promulgated rules indicate awards are subject to funding. As a result, the program is coded as 1 for first-come, first-served for all years. Awards are made in equal installments each term throughout the academic year. The award may be renewed three times for a total of four years, or the period required for the completion of the program of study. The periods of attendance for which awards are made must be consecutive academic years, which indicates an expectation for continuous enrollment.

Program eligibility requirements include:

1. Be a TN resident and attend an eligible TN college or university full-time; and
2. Be a dependent of a TN law enforcement officer, fireman, or an emergency technician at the time of the incident; and
3. Complete a FAFSA (language added in AY13: “and have a valid EFC”); and
4. Submit additional documentation detailing that the parent who was a law enforcement officer, fireman, or emergency medical service technician was killed or is now permanently disabled while performing duties within the scope of such employment. [Text taken from Dependent Children Scholarship, 2023.]

In academic year 2012-2013, the program website added the following language: students must submit the FAFSA “and have a valid EFC” (Dependent Children Scholarship, 2021). Program code provides no indication of what a “valid EFC” represents. We do not consider DCS to be a need-based aid program.

The annual program application deadline is July 15. Students submit their complete DCS application via the TSAC portal.

Tennessee Loan Forgiveness Programs

The State of Tennessee operates seven loan forgiveness programs over time, six of which are analyzed in this study: Minority Teaching Fellows, Tennessee Teaching Scholars, the Tennessee Math & Science Teacher Loan Forgiveness Program, the Tennessee Rural Health Loan Forgiveness Program, the Graduate Nursing Loan Forgiveness Program, and the Tennessee Future Teacher Scholarship. Each program is tied to a specific workforce sector, imposing

explicit service obligations on all program recipients. These loan programs effectively function as traditional financial aid programs, unless the service obligation goes unmet. The programs share several similarities (based on authors' review of documents):

1. No FAFSA submission is required; and
2. Recipients must be citizens and residents of both the United States and Tennessee; and
3. Recipients must not be in default on a federal Title IV educational loan or Tennessee educational loan, and not owe a refund on a federal Title IV student financial aid program or a Tennessee student financial aid program; and
4. Recipients must sign a promissory note tying their postgraduate employment to the relevant workforce sector before receiving any funds.

Three of the loan forgiveness programs offer aid only to students seeking advanced degrees: Math & Science, Graduate Nursing, and Rural Health.

Minority Teaching Fellows Program

First established in 1989, the Minority Teaching Fellows program (hereafter referred to as MTF) is a merit-based aid program intended to “encourage talented minority Tennesseans to enter the teaching field in Tennessee” (Minority Teaching Fellows Program, 2020). MTF awards provide \$5,000 per year for students who enroll in a teacher certification program at an eligible Tennessee college or university.

According to MTF administrative code, a “minority” student is a person who is:

African American, a person having origins in any of the black racial groups of Africa; Hispanic, a person of Mexican, Puerto Rican, Cuban, Central or South American, or other Spanish culture or origin, regardless of race; Asian American, a person having origins in any of the original peoples of the Far East, Southeast Asia, the Indian subcontinent, or the Pacific Islands; or Native American, a person having origins in any of the original peoples of North America. [NOTE: This definition does not change over time.] (Text taken from Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-13-.02, 2014.)

Eligible students include: high school seniors who have achieved at least a 2.75 high school cumulative grade point average, and either scored a minimum composite score of 18 on the ACT or 860 SAT (math and critical reading only), or be in the top 25 percent of their high school graduation class; or, continuing college students who have achieved at least a 2.5 cumulative grade point average (Minority Teaching Fellows Program, 2020).

MTF funds are intended primarily for use at Tennessee’s public four-year institutions. However, MTF funds may also be granted to students admitted to or enrolled in an accredited two-year institution of higher education, provided that a plan of study is pursued which is transferable to a college or university in Tennessee and will lead to licensure, which will then be used to teach in a public school at some prekindergarten, kindergarten, elementary, or secondary level in the State, provided that the plan of study can be completed within a four-year period calculated from the date of the first disbursement (Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-13-.03, 2013).

MTF applicants must submit their application materials by April 15. The program is considered first-come, first-serve because “awards are very competitive and based on funding,” but the

program does not impose a deadline for priority consideration (Minority Teaching Fellows Program, 2020). It does not appear that students are required to submit FAFSA documentation alongside the stand-alone MTF application via the Tennessee Student Assistance Corporation (TSAC) online application portal.

MTF student eligibility requirements through FY21 include:

1. Be a minority; and
2. Be admitted to or enrolled in an accredited institution of higher education in Tennessee from which credits earned are recognized by the State to be applicable to a teacher certification program. Loans may also be granted to students admitted to or enrolled in an accredited two-year institution of higher education, provided that a plan of study is pursued which is transferable to a college or university in Tennessee and will lead to licensure, which will then be used to teach in a public school at some prekindergarten, kindergarten, elementary, or secondary level in the State, provided that the plan of study can be completed within a four-year period calculated from the date of the first disbursement; and
3. Submit to TSAC a signed Statement of Intent to teach in a Tennessee public prekindergarten, kindergarten, elementary, or secondary school; and
4. Not accept any financial aid that carries with it a conflicting service obligation. For the purposes of this program, participation in the Tennessee Teaching Scholars Program shall be considered as accepting aid that carries a conflicting service obligation; and
5. Submit a completed application to TSAC by the established deadline on a TSAC-approved application; and
6. Submit to TSAC copies of all official transcripts and the most recent test scores; and
7. Agree to inform TSAC in writing when any significant change in status occurs and provide documentation to support it. This shall include, but is not limited to, changes in name, address, and enrollment. After obtaining teacher licensure, the recipient shall inform TSAC when they have obtained a teaching position, changed teaching assignments, or terminated teaching service. [Text taken from Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs.1640-01-13-.03, 2013.]

In FY22, program eligibility requirements are amended, which changes the program's overall target population to focus solely on current enrolled college students:

- 1) Be a minority TN resident and a U.S. citizen; and
- 2) Be classified as a college junior, senior, or graduate student; and
- 3) Be a full-time undergraduate student enrolled in courses creditable to teacher certification; or
- 4) Be at least a half-time graduate student enrolled in courses creditable to teacher certification; and
- 5) Possess a 2.5 cumulative grade point average or higher if required by the teacher education program at the student's institution of higher education; and
- 6) Not be a licensed teacher. [Text taken from Minority Teaching Fellows, 2021.]

Application materials must include:

1. A 250-word essay on "Why I Chose Teaching as a Profession"; and
2. Two recommendation letters: one from a school official and one from a person in the applicant's community; and
3. A list of extracurricular activities; and
4. An official high school transcript with official ACT/SAT scores for high school applicants or an official college transcript for continuing college students; and

5. A signed Promissory Note to teach full-time in a Tennessee public prekindergarten, kindergarten, elementary, or secondary school, one (1) year of service for each year an award is received. [Text taken from Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs.1640-01-13-.03, 2013.]

A grace period of one year is granted to allow recipients opportunity to secure employment to begin cancellation credit accrual (Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-13-.05, 2014). If recipients do not meet their obligations, the award must be repaid to TSAC. Repayment will begin if the recipient does not complete the plan of study or is not employed at an eligible PreK-12 school. When a repayment schedule is imposed, the interest accrues at nine percent from the date of graduation or withdrawal from the program (Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-13-.05, 2014).

MTF program administrative code makes no mention of eligibility for incarcerated students or undocumented students.

Tennessee Teaching Scholars

The Tennessee Teaching Scholars program (hereafter referred to as TTS) was established by Public Act in 1996. The program is intended to “encourage exemplary students to enter the teaching field in Tennessee. Participation is limited to college juniors, seniors, and post-baccalaureate candidates admitted to a teacher education program in a Tennessee college or university” across the state’s public and private, two- and four-year sectors (Tennessee Teaching Scholars, 2020). A review of historical program webpages and administrative code indicates that TTS did not offer an application cycle during academic year 2020-2021, making 2019-2020 the last cohort of students to receive TTS aid.

No FAFSA submission is required for this merit-based aid program. Annual award amounts are unknown for undergraduate students.

TTS student eligibility requirements include:

1. Be a Tennessee resident and a U.S. citizen; and
2. Have at least a 2.75 cumulative GPA or higher (if required for the teacher education program at the school of choice); and
3. Be enrolled full-time if undergraduate and at least half-time if a graduate student; and
4. Not be a licensed teacher or receive the scholarship while employed in a teaching position; and
5. Submit a signed Statement of Intent to teach full-time, one year for each year an award is received; and
6. Submit a Letter of Recommendation from an official of a State-approved teacher education program to which the student has been admitted; and
7. Not accept any financial aid that carries with it a conflicting service obligation. Participation in the Minority Teaching Fellows program shall be considered as accepting aid that carries a conflicting service obligation; and
8. Shall now owe a refund or repayment on any grant and is not in default on any loan received at any postsecondary institution, under the provisions of Title IV of the Higher Education Act of 1965, as amended. (Text taken from Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs.1640-01-17-.03, 2013.)

Students submit TTS applications via the Tennessee Student Assistance Corporation (TSAC) portal). Completed application must be submitted by April 15. Applications must include:

1. A letter of recommendation from an official of a state-approved teacher education program, attesting to the applicant's commitment to teaching and potential for success as a teacher; and
2. Official copies of all college or university transcripts and documentation verifying the standardized test scores used for admission to the teacher education program. (Text taken from Tennessee Teaching Scholars Program, 2020.)

Students receive a grace period of one year that will begin on the date the student completes their plan of study, during which repayment is not required (Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-17-.05, 2014). Repayment will begin if the recipient does not complete the plan of study or is not employed at an eligible PreK-12 school. Interest accrues at nine percent from the date of each disbursement. Recipients must be employed as a full-time teacher to be considered for forgiveness (Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-17-.05, 2014).

TTS is coded as a first-come, first-serve program because “awards are very competitive and are based on limited funding” (Tennessee Teaching Scholars Program, 2020). Renewal applicants are given first priority. Applicants seeking initial licensure are considered.

Graduate Nursing Loan-Forgiveness Program

Established April 1976, the Graduate Nursing Loan-Forgiveness program (hereafter referred to as GNLF) is “designed to encourage Tennessee residents who are registered nurses to become teachers and administrators in Tennessee nursing education programs” (Graduate Nursing Loan Forgiveness Program, 2020). The program does not indicate any need- or merit-based eligibility requirements for applicants, nor any combination thereof. GNLF recipients must be enrolled in eligible nursing education programs across the state's public and private, two- and four-year sectors.

The maximum award amount is seven thousand dollars (\$7,000) per year during periods of full-time enrollment and three thousand five hundred dollars (\$3,500) per year during periods of part-time enrollment (Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-03-.04, 2013).

Participants in GNLF “incur an obligation to enter a faculty or administrative position at a college or university in Tennessee in a nursing education program” (Graduate Nursing Loan Forgiveness Program, 2020). Students are obligated to serve four years in a faculty or administrative position following graduation in order to have the loan forgiven. If recipients do not meet this obligation the award must be repaid. Participants are allowed a grace period of three months, which begins when the borrower either completes their eligible academic program or no longer meets graduate nursing loan eligibility requirements, and during which period of time interest does not accrue and repayment is not required (Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-03-.02, 2014). Interest will accrue at the rate of nine percent per year starting at the end of the grace period (Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-03-.06, 2014).

Students apply for GNLF via the Tennessee Student Assistance Corporation's (TSAC) online application portal. We code the program as first-come, first-serve because “awards are very competitive and are based on funding” (Graduate Nursing Loan Forgiveness Program, 2020). TSAC must receive the application by March 1 – this is considered a “priority application date”

according to the program’s administrative code (Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-03-.02, 2014).

Award recipients must attend an eligible Tennessee college or university and be enrolled in a graduate program accredited by the National League for Nursing Accrediting Commission (NLNAC) and/or by the Commission on Collegiate Nursing Education (CCNE), which must also be approved by the Tennessee Board of Nursing and “lead to a master’s or post-master's degree in a field of study which will qualify the graduate to become a teacher or administrator in a college or university education program in Tennessee” (Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-03-.02, 2014).

GRLF student eligibility requirements include:

- 1) Hold an unencumbered Tennessee Registered Nurse License; and
- 2) Be enrolled either part-time or full-time in an eligible academic program at an eligible postsecondary institution (Eligibility is limited to four (4) years of full-time enrollment, or the equivalent part-time enrollment, with one (1) year of full-time enrollment equaling two (2) years of part-time enrollment. Eligibility is subject to the availability of funds); and
- 3) Provide written evidence of the student’s intention to become employed full-time or part-time in a Tennessee nursing educational program in a teaching or administrative capacity; and
- 4) Maintain satisfactory academic progress; and
- 5) Agree to inform TSAC in writing when any change occurs in name, address, or school enrollment, and provide supporting documentation. After completing the program, the recipient shall continue to notify TSAC of any change in name or address, and when the recipient has obtained a teaching or administrative position, changed teaching or administrative positions, or terminated teaching or administrative positions. (Text taken from Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-03-.03, 2013.)

Tennessee Math & Science Teacher Loan Forgiveness Program

Established in 2006, the Tennessee Math & Science Teacher Loan Forgiveness program (hereafter referred to as TMST) “provides financial assistance to Tennessee public school teachers seeking an advanced degree in a math or a science, or a certification to teach a math or a science” (Tennessee Math and Science Teacher Loan Forgiveness Program, 2020). “Science” refers to the study of biology, botany, chemistry, physics, zoology, geology, and other natural and physical sciences (Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-20-.02, 2007). The program provides aid to students enrolled in eligible academic programs across the states’ public and private, two- and four-year sectors. Program code does not stipulate any need- or merit-based aid eligibility requirements, nor any combination thereof.

TMST recipients are awarded \$2,000 per academic year, regardless of the number of terms enrolled within that academic year. The total amount of TMST funds a recipient may receive over time shall not exceed ten thousand dollars (\$10,000) for all years required for the teacher’s program of study (Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-20-.04, 2007).

Loan forgiveness requires employment in a Tennessee public school system two years for each year of loan funding received. TMST recipients are allowed a grace period of three months

which begins when the borrower either completes their eligible academic program or no longer meets the TMST eligibility requirements (Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-20-.02, 2007). Interest will not be charged for a TMST loan (Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-20-.06, 2007). Repayment will begin at the end of the grace period and continue in monthly installments over a period of no more than eight (8) years, provided that payments are a minimum of \$100 per month (Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-20-.07, 2007).

Applicants must submit TMST forms annually; both the application form and the promissory note must be submitted via the Tennessee Student Assistance Corporation's (TSAC) online portal. The application deadline is September 1 for students enrolling in Fall, February 1 for students enrolling in Spring, and May 1 for students enrolling in Summer (Tennessee Math and Science Teacher Loan Forgiveness Program, 2020).

TMST eligibility requirements include:

1. Be a citizen of the United States; and
2. Be a citizen of Tennessee; and
3. Be a resident of Tennessee, as defined by regulations promulgated by the Tennessee Board of Regents for the state university and community college system, under the authority of T.C.A. § 49-8-104 [2016] where applicable for one year immediately preceding the date of application; and
4. Be a tenured teacher teaching in a Tennessee public school system; and
5. Comply with the United States selective service requirement for registration, as such requirements are applicable to the student; and
6. Not be in default on a federal Title IV educational loan or a Tennessee educational loan; and
7. Be in compliance with federal drug-free rules and laws for receiving financial assistance; and
8. Not be incarcerated; and
9. Be admitted to and attend an eligible postsecondary institution seeking an advanced degree in a math or a science or certification to teach math or a science; and
10. Agree to teach math or a science in a Tennessee public school system two academic years for each year funds are provided by this program and sign a promissory note that stipulates the cash repayment obligation incurred if the teaching service is not fulfilled; and
11. Maintain satisfactory academic progress in the teacher's program of study with no minimum number of hours required per semester; and
12. Complete the program of study within five years beginning with the first terms for which the loan was awarded; and
13. Not allow a break in enrollment at an eligible postsecondary institution of more than twelve months. If the break in enrollment exceeds twelve months, the borrower enters the grace period followed by repayment. [Text taken from Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-20-.03, 2007.]

The program's administrative code specifies no requirements for full-time, part-time, or continuous enrollment, nor does the code provide access to aid for undocumented students.

Tennessee Rural Health Loan Forgiveness Program

The Tennessee Rural Health Loan Forgiveness program (hereafter referred to as TRH) was established through the Tennessee Rural Health Act of 2008, which set up a five-year pilot program that provided loans and loan forgiveness to Tennessee health care providers and dentists

who enrolled in the states' public and private, two- and four-year sectors (Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-21-.01, 2009). TRH ceased offering new awards after the 2012-2013 academic year (Tennessee Rural Health Loan Forgiveness Program, 2013).

Recipients had to be enrolled in eligible academic programs across the state's public and private, two- and four-year sectors. The program's administrative code does not specific any need- or merit-based aid eligibility requirements, nor any combination thereof. TRH awards did not exceed twelve thousand dollars (\$12,000) per academic year (Tennessee Rural Health Loan Forgiveness Program, 2012).

Participation in TRH loan forgiveness "require[d] health care providers and dentists to locate and practice in a Tennessee health resource shortage area after becoming licensed to practice" (Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-21-.01, 2009). If the service obligation was not met, the amount became a loan that must be repaid plus interest at nine percent (9%) annually from the date of disbursement (Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-21-.06, 2009). TRH recipients were allowed a grace period of up to twelve (12) months which begins when the borrower either completes the program of study or no longer meets the TRH eligibility requirements, during which repayment was not required (Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-21-.02, 2009).

Applicants submitted documentation through the Tennessee Student Assistance Corporation's (TSAC) online portal and the application deadline was September 1 (Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-21-.05, 2009).

TRH eligibility requirements included:

1. Be a citizen of Tennessee; and
2. Be a resident of Tennessee as defined by regulation promulgated by the Tennessee Board of Regents for the state university and community college system, under the authority of T.C.A. § 49-8-104 [2016] where applicable and under the rules of the University of Tennessee system as of the date of application and on the date of reapplication for the loan each academic year; and
3. Comply with the United States selective Service system requirement for registration, as such requirements are applicable to the borrower; and
4. Not be in default on a federal Title IV educational loan or Tennessee educational loan; and
5. Be in compliance with federal drug-free rules and laws for receiving financial assistance (being compliant means for felony possession of or selling of illegal drug charges while receiving Federal Student Aid); and
6. Not be incarcerated; and
7. Be admitted to and attend an eligible postsecondary institution seeking an advanced degree in an eligible program of study; and
8. As a service obligation of this loan, the borrower agrees to:
 1. Practice medicine in a health resource shortage area after becoming a Tennessee licensed physician, osteopathic physician, or physician assistant or receiving a Tennessee certificate of fitness as a nurse practitioner for one year for each year of funding provided by TRH and sign a promissory note that stipulates the cash repayment obligation incurred with interest if the service obligation is not fulfilled; or
 2. Practice dentistry in a health resource shortage area after becoming a licensed Tennessee dentist one year for each year of funding provided by TRH and sign a promissory note

that stipulates the cash repayment obligation incurred with interest if the service obligation is not fulfilled.

9. Maintain satisfactory academic progress in the program of study in which the borrower is enrolled; and
10. Complete the program of study in this five-year pilot program no later than Spring 2013; and
11. Not accept any other financial assistance that carries with it a service obligation after graduation and receipt of the applicable license to practice medicine or dentistry, except for a service obligation in the United States armed forces, reserve, or the National Guard. The service obligation period shall not exceed six years. (Text taken from Tenn. Comp. R. & Regs. 1640-01-21-.03, 2009.)

The program did not include any stipulations regarding full-time, part-time, or continuous enrollment. No pathways to aid access were available for incarcerated or undocumented students.

Tennessee Future Teacher Scholarship

The Tennessee Future Teacher Scholarship (hereafter referred to as TFTS) is “a loan-scholarship program intended to encourage exemplary students to enter the teaching field in Tennessee” (College for TN, 2023). Participation is limited to college juniors and seniors admitted to an approved educator preparation program (EPP) in a four-year public or private college or university. The aid program is subject to available funding. TSAC will administer the program as a five-year pilot program, beginning with the 2023-2024 academic year and terminating on July 1, 2028 (T.C.A. § 49-4-701, 2023).

Eligible students are able to enroll at public and private four-year institutions using TFTS aid. However, enrollment is restricted to teacher preparation programs approved by the state board of education at an eligible postsecondary institution.

For students attending a public institution, the award amount will be tuition and mandatory fees, less gift aid. For students attending a private institution, the award cannot exceed the average cost of tuition and mandatory fees as the state’s public institutions less gift aid.

Program eligibility requirements include:

- 1) Be a resident who graduated from an eligible high school or complete high school in a home school program; and
- 2) Not be ineligible for the scholarship under § 49-4-904; and
- 3) Achieve a final overall high school grade point average of at least 3.0 or have attained a composite ACT score of at least 21 on any single ACT test date or a concordant equivalent score on the SAT on any single SAT test date; and
- 4) Be admitted to an enrolled in an approved EPP; and
- 5) Complete scholarship application developed by TSAC; and
- 6) Complete the FAFSA each academic year annually; and
- 7) Maintain a cumulative grade point average of 2.75 in an approved EPP; and
- 8) Agree to teach in a targeted setting for at least four years after the candidate completes an approved EPP; and
- 9) Be eligible for, and receive, a TN HOPE Scholarship; and

- 10) Submit a letter of recommendation from an official of the EPP at the eligible postsecondary institution. [Text taken from TN Senate Bill 1220, 2023.]

A “targeted setting” includes either: 1) a TN public school located in a distressed or at-risk county, as determined by the Department of Education, or 2) a subject area for which there is a critical shortage, as determined by the Department of Education (TN S.B.1220, 2023).

Students must complete the scholarship application and email the completed application to a program contact by September 1 for consideration.

Aid termination criteria include:

- 1) The student has attained a degree through an approved EPP; and
- 2) The student ceases to be eligible for the TN HOPE Scholarship; and
- 3) Three years have elapsed since the date of the student’s enrollment in a term for which the student first received the TN Future Teacher Scholarship. [Text taken from T.C.A. § 49-4-701, 2023.]

Though the program webpages and administrative code do not explicitly reference a requirement for continuous enrollment, we code the variable as 1 given the time limit on aid.

If a student receives TFTS and does not teach in a targeted setting for at least four consecutive years, then the student must reimburse TSAC for each year the student did not teach in a targeted setting in an amount equal to the total scholarship amount the student received pursuant to TFTS divided by four, without interest.

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Appendix B: List of TN State Aid Programs Excluded from Data Collection

Dual Enrollment Grant

The Dual Enrollment Grant is established and funded from the net proceeds of the state lottery and “awarded to students who are attending an eligible high school and who are also enrolled in college courses at eligible postsecondary institutions for which they will receive college credit” (Dual Enrollment Grant, 2022). The program is active for FY24.

John R. Justice Student Loan Repayment Program

“Congress enacted the John R. Justice Prosecutors and Defenders Incentive Act (42 U.S.C. 3797cc-21) to encourage qualified attorneys to choose careers as prosecutors and public defenders and to continue that service. The program provides loan repayment assistance for local, state, and federal public defenders and local and state prosecutors who commit to continued employment as public defenders and prosecutors for at least three years. The Bureau of Justice Assistance awarded federal funds to all fifty states and the District of Columbia to serve eligible recipients working within their respective jurisdiction” (John R. Justice Student Loan Repayment Program, 2013). The program operated in Tennessee during academic years 2012-2014.

Middle College Scholarship

“Begun in the Fall 2018 semester, the Middle College Scholarship is established and funded from the proceeds of the state lottery and awarded to high school juniors and seniors enrolled full-time at an eligible postsecondary institution” (Middle College Scholarship, 2022). The program is active for FY24.

Reduction in Force Tuition Assistance Benefit

“Tuition assistance of up to \$11,600 (\$5,800 per year) at the schools, institutions, and entities governed by the Tennessee Board of Regents and the University of Tennessee Board of Trustees, as well as state certified apprenticeship programs. Tuition assistance benefits are available for a two-year period beginning when an employee is separated due to a reduction in force. GED classes are also available through the Tennessee Department of Labor and Workforce Development’s Career Centers, and testing fees will be covered under the tuition assistance benefit. This program is not offered to the general public, but only as one of the benefits provided to State employees who are impacted by the Reduction in Force” (Reduction in Force Tuition Assistance Benefit, 2022). The program is active for FY24.

TSAC-Byrd Scholarship Program

“The TSAC-Byrd Scholarship program, formerly the Robert C. Byrd Honors Scholarship Program was intended to promote student excellence and achievement, and to recognize exceptional students who show promise of continued excellence... TSAC was notified that funding for this program was eliminated from the federal budget. Therefore TSAC [was] unable

to offer new awards to students starting with the 2011-2012 academic year” (TSAC-Byrd Scholarship Program, 2011).

Voluntary Buyout Program - Tuition Assistance Benefit

“Tuition assistance of up to \$15,600 (\$7,800 per year) at the schools, institutions, and entities governed by the Tennessee Board of Regents and the University of Tennessee Board of trustees, as well as certified apprenticeship programs. Tuition assistance benefits are available for a two-year period beginning when an employee is separated due to the voluntary buyout program. GED classes are also available through the Tennessee Department of Labor and Workforce Development’s Career Centers, and testing fees will be covered under the tuition assistance benefit. This program is not offered to the general public, but only as one of the benefits provided to State employees who are impacted by the Voluntary Buyout Program” (Voluntary Buyout Program - Tuition Assistance Benefit, 2022). The program is active for FY24.

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Appendix C. Random effects regression results for weighted administrative burden index (2011-2024)

Table 3. Random effects regression results (2011-2024)

Targeted population	Random effects results	List of program(s) targeted toward specific population
Students with financial need	-2.775 (1.640)	Student Assistance Award, HOPE Non-Traditional, HOPE Access, HOPE Aspire (n=4)
Racially minoritized students	7.132*** (0.702)	Minority Teacher Fellows (n=1)
Only students at technical and community colleges	-3.940** (1.252) (0.260)	Community College Reconnect, TCAT Reconnect, Wilder-Naifeh Technical Skills Grant (n=3)
Students meeting specific academic thresholds	3.444** (1.303)	HOPE Access, HOPE Aspire, HOPE Foster Child, General Assembly Merit, HOPE, McAuliffe Scholarship, Ned McWherter Scholarship, Minority Teaching Fellows, HOPE Non-traditional, Future Teacher Scholarship, Teaching Scholars (n=11)
Only students at four-year universities	0.115 (0.260) (1.252)	HOPE Non-traditional, STEP UP, Future Teacher Scholarship (n=3)
Number of observations	251	

Notes. Program elements that require sustained effort are weighted double in the weighted administrative burden index. Results come from separate regression models in which programs are coded as 1 if they are targeted toward the specific population of students and all other state aid programs in Tennessee are coded as 0 (referent group). All models control for average aid award (logged) and year fixed effects. The outcome is the level of administrative burden in a given program in a given year. Robust standard errors are clustered in parentheses.

* p<.05, ** p<.01 *** p<.001

Appendix D. Weighted administrative burden index for state aid programs in Tennessee in 2024

Notes. Program elements that require sustained effort are weighted double in the weighted administrative burden index. For 6 programs that were discontinued prior to 2024, we used the most recent year the program was active. These programs were the Rural Health Loan Forgiveness (2013), Community College Reconnect Grant (2018), McAuliffe Scholarship (2020), HOPE Access (2021), Math and Science Teacher Loan Forgiveness (2021), and Teaching Scholars (2021).